

SOCLIMPACT

Downscaling climate impacts and decarbonisation pathways in EU Islands, and enhancing socioeconomic and non-market evaluation of Climate Change for Europe, for 2050 and beyond

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Work Package 7:

Ranking and Mapping transition pathways in islands and enabling networking and information system for regional and EU policy design

Deliverable 7.1. Conceptual Framework.

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1 Overview Pathway framework structure for European Islands

In the current approach the term “scenario”, defines how the future might be developing, considering the socio-economic, climate change, and climate change policy contexts, the term “pathways” refers to the time-dependent variation of the conditions of a specific component of the future (e.g. socio-economy or climate change) (van Vuuren *et al.*, 2014a).

As well as the concept of pathway defined by IPCC in the IPCC AR5 and SR1.5 the Project considers the temporal evolution of systems towards a future state and aim to strengthen the quantitative and qualitative components of the potential future scenarios or storylines development and orientation for decision-making processes or societal goals.

STEP 1 – This step defines the RISK PATHWAY component that brings to decision relevant variables introducing a measurement method that will be used to characterizes the climates change risk in a transversal way in WP7. In this context the WP3/4 will provide risk assessment indicators, disaggregated in hazard and intermediate impacts, vulnerability and exposure variables. Those variables will be originally generated in WP4, WP5 and WP6 and the risk assessment produced constitutes the base on adaptation pathway decisions. For instance, the framework allows to incorporate indicators to assess risk and socio-economic impacts in a quantitative way, defining adaptation policy pathways in the context of European islands.

In paralleled, to enrich the information for decision in Island context three different sources of information were organized and developed in STEP 2, STEP 3 and STEP 4. Those steps are complementary to the risk assessment indicators developed in STEP 1 and aim to feed WP7 with critical information and regarding: Climate models on STEP 2, defined as hazard and intermediate impacts and witch change within different Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs); Socio-economic models and narratives on STEP 3, defined also as exposure and vulnerability (on WP3) and witch can change within different Shared Socio-economic Pathways (SSPs); and climate adaptation policies on STEP 4, defined as Shared Policy Assumptions (SPA) in the context of the framework applied.

STEP 2 – This step defines the CLIMATE PATHWAY projected for the future and is organized in RCPs. The climate modeled output information from WP4 will be constituted as climate Hazard and Impacts variable and will be use do define the final pathways.

STEP 3 - This step defines the SOCIO-ECONOMIC PATHWAY by using the concept of Shared Socio-economic Pathways (SSPs) and downscaling/ extending EU SSPs trend in to Island SSPs in the Blue Economy Sectors shaped for SOCLIMPACT.

STEP 4 - This step defines the CLIMATE ADAPTATION POLICIES PATHWAY by using the concept SPA and promoting the identify policies: Screening of islands' climate policies. SPAs which include: (1) climate policy goals; (2) policy regimes and measures; and (3) implementation limits and obstacles. Will be identified adaptation options under the various broad categories that are relevant for the sectors and islands context under develop.

STEP 5 - Define pathway alternatives (SSP-RCP-SPA). The layers of information developed in STEP 2, STEP 3 and STEP 4 will support the decisions at the Island/Archipelago scale, defining

the boundary conditions on adaptation (considering DRR) policy pathways. This methodologic step will be fed by the Stakeholder analysis and contribution in workshop environment and to create local pathway alternatives that will provide priorities on adaptation pathways) - STEP 6. On the development adaptation policies, critical decisions may have to be made in an uncertainty context. Adaptation policy pathways will be developed seeing the socio-economic characteristics and context of island territories.

STEP 6 – Is mainly the development and implementation of the workshops with the main objective is to develop adaptation pathways for the Islands involved in SOCLIMPACT. The participatory process is a meeting through which stakeholders and SOCLIMPACT IFP and experts (models and sectors) collaborate develop, test and validate the adaptation pathways. The main purpose of the participatory process is: (1) present the relevant climate change, socio-economic tendencies and alternative SOCLIMPACT pathways; (2) incorporate views of different stakeholders in the Islands; (3) create adaptation pathways for different time steps. Stakeholders are asked to create adaptation pathways based on adaptation option offered under a scenario based on RCP8.5 and SSP2 conditions. The aim is to create a pathway that best match with what is the stakeholder's knowledge and expectations. Stakeholders will be asked also to identify potential barriers on the implementation of the chosen pathway.

STEP 7 – how all this can be organized as a guidance for the future development. How we can extrapolate the scenario based on RCP8.5 and SSP2 to other scenarios.

Figure 1 - Framework and methodological steps for the development of climate change pathways.

The current Framework aim to follow the IPCC guidelines for the creation of scenario and decision on climate change. Regarding this and as described in “A new scenario framework for Climate Change Research: scenario matrix architecture” (van Vuuren *et al.*, 2014a), to develop integrated scenarios, a set of different components - pathways - and their time-dependency, were considered in order to facilitate climate change research and assessments in different contexts. Those components are:

- 1) Socio-economic pathway (SSPs);
- 2) Projected future climate associated with radiative forcing pathways (RCPs);
- 3) Shared Policy Assumptions (SPAs).

To be consistent with this scenario development structure and with the objectives of SOCLIMPACT and to achieve an output based on the best practices used in climate change policy pathways research, we propose a methodology to create local pathways which considers these three components.

Therefore, the scenarios creation will consider socio-economic pathways (SSPs), associated metrics (e.g. GDP and population – given by WP6) and the climate information (based on RCPs – given by WP4). SSP and RCP together will establish a common ground for the future work and useful information to deal with the climate risks.

Furthermore, the development of pathways are based on scenarios which describe likely societal developments and the associated anthropogenic drivers of climate change (i.e., greenhouse gases, chemically reactive gases, aerosols, and land use). This rationale allows coherent assessment of changes in the climate system, impacts, and responses under a wide range of future outcomes.

Due to this policy framework is built around components that combine climate forcing (RCPs) and socio-economic conditions (SSPs) we can define conditions in which adaptation and DRR can be evaluated or assessed in the context of the Islands.

Consequently, in SOCLIMPACT the SSPs and SPAs will be used to define the limits of how the future climate change impacts (RCPs and projected climate change) could be tackled. In parallel to the analysis of RCPs and climate change, new socioeconomic storylines were created (and quantified with integrated assessment models) quantifying the SSPs and associated emissions scenarios, which allows for the assessment of climate vulnerability and impacts.

The scenarios framework (van Vuuren *et al.*, 2014a) was incorporated into the framework of SOCLIMPACT to achieve the objectives defined for WP7. The SOCLIMPACT framework allows the development of a consistent architecture that establishes the links between: (1) the methodological steps and timeframe of SOCLIMPACT; the (2) Impact Chains and the scenario framework.

The SOCLIMPACT framework is designed to combine a participatory approach (considering Sector Partners, IFPs and the stakeholders in the regions) to downscale the EU SSPs focusing on the literature available at European level.

The aims, objectives and scope regarding work about policy pathways are:

- ✓ Create Blue Economy sector pathways and scenarios on climate change at the island scale in a European context;
- ✓ Develop a framework for policy and decision making in the islands' context that enable the assessment of the socio-economic implications of climate change and opportunities that may emerge;
- ✓ Combine different climate projections (based on RCPs) with scenarios of socioeconomic conditions (based on SSPs) and assess impacts, incorporating the outputs and results provided by other WPs deliverables;
- ✓ Develop adaptation scenarios - Shared Policy Assumptions (SPAs);¹
- ✓ Develop criteria to test and prioritize SPAs (policy options) under different scenarios (SSP-RCP) considering the islands' context;
- ✓ Incorporate risk assessment developed in the project (WP3 and WP4) in the pathways of adaptation development.

The Framework is developed to mainstream adaptation in Blue Economy sectors, defined as Energy, Coastal and Maritime Tourism, Aquaculture and Maritime Transport. The current document also clarifies definitions, scope and boundaries of sectors in the specific context of the Islands and interaction with climate change policy and potential impacts.

Furthermore, Coastal and Maritime Tourism sector was considered with an open scope inside the economy system. In this context, the Project develop the whale watching case study to experience the application of the framework in a more constrain scope of analysis and geographical scale.

¹ Across the project as a whole it was decided to exclude the mitigation pathway from the core of the pathway developed

2 Framework Application Steps

2.1 STEP 1 - RISK pathway – Risk assessment

Responsible partners: All WP7 partners

Links to other work packages: input from WP3 and WP4

This step will be implemented in D7.3/T7.3 and D7.4/T7.4 and will follow the Impact Chains (IC) developed in WP3 and the risk assessment, based on IC, developed in WP4.

STEP 1.1 – This step aims to prioritize and select the six most relevant IC (Zebisch *et al.*, 2017a) for each Island considering two alternative methods: (1) consider the risk assessment developed in WP4; (2) Use IFP expert judgment to define a level of risk considering disaggregated factors evaluation of hazard (using RCP 8.5 projections), vulnerability and exposure. The IFP are encouraged to use method one but can opt for method two. Furthermore, stakeholder’s consultation is advised using appropriate engagement tools like online meetings and surveys. This risk method evaluation will consider the interpretation of the IC developed in WP3 and the IFP experience in the field (Climate Risk Levels: Very high; High; Moderate; Undetectable). See **Figure 2**)

		<< Hazards RCP8.5 >>			
Risk for which Impact Chains were developed		Hazards source?	Considered hazards	short term [2046-2065]	long term [2081-2100]
Changes in production due to changes in seawater characteristics		Model (WP4)	<i>answer</i>	-1	0
Changes in production due to changes in seawater temperature		<i>answer</i>	<i>answer</i>	-1	0
Damages in ports’ infrastructures and equipment’s due to floods and waves		<i>answer</i>	<i>answer</i>	-1	0
Decrease in water availability for the tourism industry uses		<i>answer</i>	<i>answer</i>	-1	0
Increase of damages in infrastructure and facilities due to sea level rise and storms (also for aquaculture activity)		<i>answer</i>	<i>answer</i>	-1	0

Exposure and Vulnerability source?	<< Exposure (+SSP inputs) >>			<< Vulnerability >>			[Agreement and Evidence]	[Climate HSA Level]
	Considered Exposure factors	short term [2046-2065]	long term [2081-2100]	Considered vulnerability factors	short term [2046-2065]	long term [2081-2100]		
IC Model (SMT)	<i>answer</i>	3	3	<i>answer</i>	2	2	Confidence	4
<i>answer</i>	<i>answer</i>	3	3	<i>answer</i>	2	2	Limited	3
<i>answer</i>	<i>answer</i>	3	3	<i>answer</i>	2	2	Medium	2
<i>answer</i>	<i>answer</i>	3	3	<i>answer</i>	2	2	Robust	1
<i>answer</i>	<i>answer</i>	3	3	<i>answer</i>	2	2		0
<i>answer</i>	<i>answer</i>	3	3	<i>answer</i>	2	2		0

Figure 2 – STEP 1 – Draft of Risk Assessment Evaluation Table (RAET)

STEP 1.2 – The IC Risks evaluated will be ranked in task 1.1 using the Risk Assessment Evaluation Table (RAET). For the top six IC level risks evaluated, the variables or metrics of hazard, vulnerability and exposure will be furthermore evaluated with more detail by IFP (consider the variables that already emerged from the ICs developed in WP3).

The conceptualization of exposure and vulnerability to weather and climate impacts and the likelihood of disasters (disaster risk) will be put in perspective of the socio-economic development. This conceptualization explains how disaster risk management and adaptation to climate change can be merged with exposure and vulnerability and thus risk.

STEP 1.3 – For all these evaluations an estimate will be made regarding the level of confidence on the results and/or answers. This will be based on agreement and evidence criteria (Capela Lourenço *et al.*, 2014).

2.1.1 Impact chain concept and application in step 1

The ICs definition of the scope and scale was developed in WP3 and follows the concept of Impact Chain (IC) (Zebisch *et al.*, 2017b). Risk assessment is based on the concepts of the IPCC Report: Managing the Risks of Extreme Events and Disasters to Advance Climate Change Adaptation (SREX)(IPCC, 2012) and were rearranged for climate change adaptation science in IPCC AR5 (IPCC, 2014a).

The creation of ICs emphasize the need to consider the specificity of each region in the approach to risk perception on climate change and adaptation (Taylor, Dessai and Bruine de Bruin, 2014). The integration of multiple scales in adaptation is proposed in SOCLIMPACT by developing a conceptual background to measure climate change risks through the concept of ICs which considers impacts, exposure, vulnerability and hazard. Beyond the climate hazards, the approach proposed for the risk assessment is useful to conceptualize and define the scope of adaptation and disaster risk reduction in the environmental, economic and social impacts components.

The top 6 IC will be used to create policies and define future time-led "paths" in the context of adaptation to climate change and disaster risk reduction. Thresholds and transition timeframes will be defined previously in WP4 and in the modeled IC.

The climate change risks identified for Blue Economy sectors were defined in SOCLIMPACT in WP3 and WP4 as a basis for the adoption of adaptation measures.

Table 1 - Climate change risks and Impact Chain developed in SOCLIMPACT for Blue Economy sectors on European islands (from WP3)

Changes in production due to changes in seawater characteristics
Changes in production due to changes in seawater temperature
Damages in ports' infrastructures and equipment's due to floods and waves
Decrease in water availability for the tourism industry uses
Increase of damages in infrastructure and facilities due to sea level rise and storms (also for aquaculture activity)
Increase of health issues due to emergent diseases
Increased environmental pollution from aquaculture sites due to changes in coastal hydrodynamics
Loss of attractiveness and comfort due to beach reduction
Loss of attractiveness due to increase in wildfire danger in touristic areas
Loss of attractiveness due to loss of cultural heritage
Loss of attractiveness of touristic land environments
Loss of attractiveness of touristic marine environments
Loss of comfort due to increase of thermal stress
Changes in energy demand due to changes in precipitations and temperatures
Changes in power generation due to long term climate change and variability
Damages to transmission grids due to extreme events

The list of IC selection criteria was developed with the Island Focal Points (IFP) in WP3.

In resume, STEP 1, will use the Impact Chains structure and the modeled climate change risk indicators performed to shape and prioritize the risk analysis, this approach will be used also in WP7 to define threshold or tipping points (decision points) according to different time steps, RCPs and SSP. All the climate change risks for Blue Economy sectors on European islands developed in WP3 and 4 will be used and evaluated in the context of each island. For this evaluation three alternatives will be available: (1) consider the risk and hazard indicators available for each region and IC; (2) consider other references in the context of risk and hazard that can be apply to region; (3) use pure expert judgment. The alternatives proposed can be used in parallel.

During this step we will be able to incorporate the level of confidence in the results. It will be measured the confidence on the results involving the expert judgment from the technical team member and the local experts. The level of confidence derived from a balance between the level of agreement with other studies in the region and the level of evidence, based on robustness of the models or quality of observed data (Capela Lourenço *et al.*, 2014).

For supplementary information about Impact Chains definitions and methodology see Annex.

2.2 STEP 2 - CLIMATE pathway - Climate Hazard and Impacts analysis

Responsible partners: All WP7 partners are involved

Links to other work packages: input from WP3 and WP4

This step will be implemented in D7.2/T7.2 and D7.3/T7.3 and will follow the outputs developed in WP4 (D4.5).

STEP 2.1 – Map the territory with enough resolution and add available variables and datasets climate data gaps for each island.

STEP 2.2 – In this task all the relevant information produced by the climate models developed in the Project will be gathered. It will be defined and collected the climate hazard time tendencies (short term [2046-2065] and long term [2081-2100]) for each island.

STEP 2.3 – From the top six IC risks defined in Step 1.2 for each island we will identify and define the climate Hazards factors that are relevant to characterize each Island. For those factors it will be created a Summary of Change and a description and a Snapshot of Anticipated Changes. The hazard tendencies will be also organized in two types of change: gradual climatic changes (changes in averages) and changes in intensity or/and frequency of extreme events (e.g.: storms, droughts, floods).

STEP 2.4 –Validate the climate change hazard future tendencies created in WP4 and together with modelers (WP4 team) define the level confidence in the results (as it is done in Step 1.3).

STEP 2.5 – The climate information regionalized for each island will be evaluated by the IFPs regarding its applicability in Local Working Groups.

2.2.1 Climate information in Step 2

The information about climate hazards and impacts will be created in WP4. In this context the project aims to assess the impacts of climate change through the development of relevant information from the large-scale to the local and sectoral effects of climate change, using regional climate models. This information is useful to identify, test, and prioritize policy options, in parallel with the vulnerability assessment developed in *Step 1*.

The runs of the models in WP4 will aim to characterize climate change-induced modifications in the local environment of islands. This step will translate the information obtained from climate models into relevant and useful information to users and to develop the policy pathways in the islands. Additionally, for Islands which data are not available alternatives for supporting decision making should be studied and prepared together with the climate data providers inside the Project.

Box 1.1: Whale watching case study: Example of step 2 application

The selection of relevant climate variables for whale watching was derived from the literature and identified in the hazard component of the IC. An assessment of each variable was carried out in WP4 considering the availability of data for the study regions and the capability of computation within SOCLIMPACT. This information was then crossed with the relevant variables identified for cetacean species. The selected variables considered were: SST and 3D temperature; Chlorophyll-a (few future projections and less robust results) and potentially wave height. The climate scenarios considered are RCP8.5, RCP 2.6 and historical scenarios for the following period: [Baseline:1986-2005] – [2046-2065] - [2081-2100] (WP4 report).

Climate models' outputs are complex and not suitable for a user/ decision-maker. Nevertheless, many options are available to incorporate this information in the decision-making framework of the Island. In SOCLIMPACT the incorporation of the IC methodology has, among others, the objective of developing a useful output that can be used for decision-making.

The climate Islands projections are crucial to measure the impacts of the socio-economic sectors and systems in the Islands. The future climate drivers constitute an important layer to analyze and evaluate risks and vulnerabilities in each of the island. The tendencies or variables that emerge from the climate projections are extremely relevant for decision-making and a wide diversity of solutions to communicate this are available, clarifying the uncertainty of the process (Step 2.4).

The climate information will be delivered within a framework that could maximize the usefulness of the information for SOCLIMPACT partners and stakeholders. The communicational solutions will be developed systematically in line with the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC).

	Climate Variable (Considered hazards)	Summary of Change	Snapshot of Anticipated Changes	Confidence
Considered hazards List				

Figure 3—Output to communicate climate change tendencies and impacts - Adapted from: (City of Vancouver, 2012)

In STEP 2, a literature review will be implemented to identify and complement the main potential impacts of climate change for the top 6 IC risks. This will consider the main climate/hazards variable already identified for each risk in a sector /island.

For supplementary information about Climate pathways or RCPs definitions and methodology see Annex.

2.3 STEP 3 - SOCIO-ECONOMIC pathway for Blue Sectors

Responsible partners: WP7 will provide the SSPs for the IFP and together with sector leaders will develop sectoral SSPs for each island.

Links to other work packages: input from WP3, WP5 and WP6

This step will be implemented in D7.2/T7.2, D7.3/T7.3, D7.4/T7.4 and will follow the outputs developed in WP6 (D6.2 and D6.3).

STEP 3.1 – In this step all the relevant information produced by the economic models will be collected in D7.2. It will be also collected the vulnerabilities and exposure factors developed inside the ICs and who can be used to measure time tendencies (short term [2046-2065] and long term [2081-2100]) for each island.

STEP 3.2 - Shared Socio-Economic Pathways development:

STEP 3.2.1 - Selection of SSPs to be considered in SOCLIMPACT.

STEP 3.2.2 - Identify SSPs narratives for the EU (or member states associated with SOCLIMPACT islands) from previous existing studies.

STEP 3.2.3 - From the EU socio-economic pathways define relevant SSP Elements (factors and associated indicators) and identify socio-economic pathways.

STEP 3.2.4 - Blue Economy Sectors SSPs development:

STEP 3.2.4a - Create Sector SSP Elements

STEP 3.2.4b - Create Sectoral SSPs narratives for each Blue Economy sector (x4)

SOCLIMPACT Aquaculture Key elements #1	Eur-SSP1		Eur-SSP3	
	<i>We are the World</i>		<i>Icarus</i>	
	short term [2046-2065]	long term [2081-2100]	short term [2046-2065]	long term [2081-2100]
Fish demand (Europe)	12.2 million tonnes (+)	11.5 million tonnes (-)	10.0 million tonnes (-)	6.9 million tonnes (--)
Total production	Medium 0 (-)		Low (-) (--)	
Percentage of production exported	Medium 0 0		Low (-) (--)	
Production costs + energy price	Medium (+) (-)		High (+) (++)	

Figure 4 – Aquaculture Sectorial SSP1 and SSP1examples

SOCLIMPACT Aquaculture Key elements #1	Eur-SSP4		Eur-SSP5	
	<i>Riders on the Storm</i>		<i>Fossil-fuelled Development</i>	
	short term [2046-2065]	long term [2081-2100]	short term [2046-2065]	long term [2081-2100]
Fish demand (Europe)	Medium		13.7 million tonnes	17.2 million tonnes
	(+)	(-)	(+)	(++)
Total production	Medium		High	
	0	0	(+)	(++)
Percentage of production exported	Medium		High	
	0	0	(+)	(++)
Production costs + energy price	High		Low	
	(+)	(++)	(-)	(--)

Figure 5 – Aquaculture Sectorial SSP4 and SSP5 examples

STEP 3.2.5. - Blue Economy Sectors SSPs downscaling for Island:

STEP 3.2.5a - Identify distinguishing features or tendencies for the Sector SSP Elements developed in STEP 3.2.4a and for each island.

STEP 3.2.5b – Adapt the sectorial SSPs narratives for each Blue Economy sector (STEP 3.3.4b) for each island.

STEP 3.3 – From the top six IC risks defined in Step 1.2 for each island we will define the Exposure and Vulnerability factors that are relevant to characterize the Island climate change vulnerability and exposure (some adjustments from the original will be made).

STEP 3.4 – The Exposure and Vulnerability factors considered in Step 3.3 will be connected to the Socio-economic indicators (output from WP6). This will allow us to compare both outputs and ensure coherency between them. The Exposure and Vulnerability indicators will be now be reevaluated considering the results of the Socio-economic indicators outlook (WP6 – D6.2). This will provide us with a Framework to define the Island economic context (which will be equivalent to SSP2).

STEP 3.5 – In this phase partners will consider SSP Pathways created in STEP 3.2 and relate them to the Socio-economic indicators (output from WP6 used in the previous step). This step will allow to extend and analyze the socio-economic indicators through different SSPs, considering the SSP2 socio-economic indicators as a base for the analysis.

	Eco Indicators - SSP Key element	SSP2 (WP6 - outlook)		
		short term	short term	long term
		[2020-2045]	[2046-2065]	[2081-2100]
SSPs	Total production	1000	4000	12000

Figure 6 - STEP 3.4 example - Blue Economy Sectors SSP2 tendencies

Tendencies							
SSP1		SSP3		SSP4		SSP5	
short term [2046-2065]	long term [2081-2100]						
0	(-)	(-)	(--)	0	0	(+)	(++)

Figure 7 - STEP 3.4 example - Blue Economy Sectors SSPs tendencies and indicators at Island level.

2.3.1 Extending SSPs to islands to develop local assumptions

This component of the framework will materialize the future socioeconomic conditions for each island in blue economy sector. This will define the groundwork for the application of the climate change policies by defining the economic context and social development status of each region and sector. The creation of socioeconomic conditions is required to complement atmospheric or oceanographic climate change drivers defined by the RCPs and their potential impact on the climate system.

Most of the studies carried out so far, focus on the extension of SSPs storylines. It is expected that the next research steps will focus on the quantification of these storylines or pathways. The SSP extensions and downscale will be performed in WP7 together with sector experts and incorporating the islands and sectors using regional distinguishing features of the sectors SSPs.

Based on the EU-SSPs (Kok *et al.*, 2018), SOCLIMPACT will create coherent storylines for the regional context. This task will be developed through four main blocks:

- (1) Sectoral SSPs: Blue Economy Sectors:

Table 2 – Sources of information to develop SSP extended narratives or storylines for Energy, Aquaculture, Tourism, Maritime Transport

Sectors	SSP storyline sources
Energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Shared Socio-Economic Pathways of the Energy Sector – Quantifying the Narratives</i> (Drouet <i>et al.</i>, 2016) – Global SSPs; - <i>The Shared Socioeconomic Pathways and their energy, land use, and greenhouse gas emissions implications: An overview</i> (Riahi <i>et al.</i>, 2017) – Global SSPs; - IMPRESSION Project (Kok and Pedde, 2016; Kok <i>et al.</i>, 2018) – EU Scenarios
Aquaculture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Socio-political scenarios for the fishery and aquaculture sectors in Europe (CERES, 2016) – EU SSPs; - <i>The State of World Fisheries and Aquaculture</i> (FAO, 2014) – Global Scenarios
Tourism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regionalized Shared Socioeconomic Pathways: narratives and spatial population projections for the Mediterranean coastal zone (Reimann, Merkens and Vafeidis, 2018);
Maritime Transport	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Atmospheric emissions of European SECA shipping: long-term projections</i> (Kalli <i>et al.</i>, 2013) - Baltic Sea;

(2) SSP2 will be modeled in WP6 will provide the quantified layer of the socio-economic context and the boundaries conditions for the regional SSPs.

For this the macroeconomic outlook for the islands' economic will be used to define each island profile and the metrics of the socioeconomic Impacts of Climate Change Scenarios will enrich the SSP storylines.

(3) Create a distinguishing feature on socio-economic context of each island.

To create distinguish feature for each Island, the IFP will work together with sector leaders and other WP7 team to develop assumptions for scenarios to provide local context to the sectors SSPs. Those assumptions will be created within the set of existing European SSPs and the Impact Chain results for Exposure.

For each territory/island it is important to consider studies and information as a starting point to develop specific narratives. Some sources of information to develop extend SSP narratives or storylines for the Islands are available in Table 7.

Table 3 – Sources of information to develop SSP extended narratives or storylines for the Islands case studies

Islands	SSP narrative sources	SSP Public Database	Other SSP Narratives alternatives
Azores	Based on SSP Public Database of the country	- Portugal Scenarios; - Model/Scenarios available; - Variables: GDP and Population	<i>Iberian socio-economic scenarios</i> from IMPRESSION Project (Kok and Pedde, 2016)
Sardinia	Based on SSP Public Database of the country	- Italia Scenarios; - Model/Scenarios available; - Variables: GDP and Population	Regionalized Shared Socioeconomic Pathways: narratives and spatial population projections for the Mediterranean coastal zone (Reimann, Merkens and Vafeidis, 2018)
Crete	Based on SSP Public Database of the country	- Greece Scenarios; - Model/Scenarios available; - Variables: GDP and Population	Regionalized Shared Socioeconomic Pathways: narratives and spatial population projections for the Mediterranean coastal zone (Reimann, Merkens and Vafeidis, 2018)
Malta	Based directly on SSP Public Database	- Malta Scenarios; - Model/Scenarios available; - Variables: GDP and Population	Regionalized Shared Socioeconomic Pathways: narratives and spatial population projections for the Mediterranean coastal zone (Reimann, Merkens and Vafeidis, 2018)
Canary Islands	Based on SSP Public Database of the country	- Spain Scenarios; - Model/Scenarios available; - Variables: GDP and Population	<i>Iberian socio-economic scenarios</i> from IMPRESSION Project (Kok and Pedde, 2016)
Corsica	Based on SSP Public Database of the country	- France Scenarios; - Model/Scenarios available; - Variables: GDP and Population	Regionalized Shared Socioeconomic Pathways: narratives and spatial population projections for the Mediterranean coastal zone (Reimann, Merkens and Vafeidis, 2018)
Madeira	Based on SSP Public Database of the country	- Portugal Scenarios; - Model/Scenarios available; - Variables: GDP and Population	<i>Iberian socio-economic scenarios</i> from IMPRESSION Project (Kok and Pedde, 2016)
Cyprus	Based directly on SSP Public Database	- Cyprus west Scenarios; - Model/Scenarios available; - Variables: GDP and Population	Regionalized Shared Socioeconomic Pathways: narratives and spatial population projections for the Mediterranean coastal zone (Reimann, Merkens and Vafeidis, 2018)
Sicily	Based on SSP Public Database of the country	- Italian Scenarios; - Model/Scenarios available; - Variables: GDP and Population	Regionalized Shared Socioeconomic Pathways: narratives and spatial population projections for the Mediterranean coastal zone (Reimann, Merkens and Vafeidis, 2018)
Fehmarn	Based on SSP Public Database of the country	- Germany Scenarios; - Model/Scenarios available; - Variables: GDP and Population	Not found
West Indies	Based directly on SSP Public Database	- Martinique, Montserrat and/or Dominica Scenarios; - Model/Scenarios available;	Under review ²

² https://www.cavehill.uwi.edu/cermes/getdoc/1986170c-0dd1-472f-9dba-f3720b242c21/drakes_et_al_2017_golocarsce-scenarios_ctr_82.aspx

		Variables: GDP and Population	
Balearic Islands	Based on SSP Public Database of the country	- Spain Scenarios; - Model/Scenarios available; - Variables: GDP and Population	Regionalized Shared Socioeconomic Pathways: narratives and spatial population projections for the Mediterranean coastal zone (Reimann, Merkens and Vafeidis, 2018) <i>Iberian socio-economic scenarios</i> from IMPRESSION Project (Kok and Pedde, 2016)

The storyline to be developed will be internally consistent tables framed in plausible futures trends (Figure 7) of evolution of the international context driving by the evolution of economy and human activities.

This will support or consolidate exploratory views on the evolution of blue economy sectors in EU islands by the end of the century. This task will open a research area for the development local socioeconomic scenarios based on the narratives using quantitative variables to support macroeconomic modeling, optimization and simulation exercises. This can be used to support the modeling of trajectories of GHG emissions compatible with the local commitment and goals.

The European SSP narrative should be downscaled for the blue economy sectors as: SSPs-Aquaculture; SSPs-Tourism; SSPs- Tourism -Whale watching; SSPs-Transport and SSPs-Energy (Frame et al., 2018).

(4) To develop local assumptions

For the sectors chosen in WP3 and the IC produced, the distinguishing features of each island will be considered and validated.

Box 1.3: Whale watching case study: Example of step 3 application

- In the SOCLIMPACT framework for the development of climate pathways, sectoral SSPs will be developed, nested in the European SSPs, to inform stakeholders of the national and regional impacts and risks to the whale watching activity. For the whale watching, two integrations will be made: 1) with the European SSPs; and 2) with the sectoral SSPs on Coastal and Maritime Tourism.
- The Whale watching SSPs will be developed in the following steps: 1) The key elements of each SSP will be identified; 2) Each SSP story outline will be constructed with

For supplementary information about socio-economic pathways definitions and methodology see Annex.

<https://www.atlanticcouncil.org/publications/reports/latin-america-and-the-caribbean-2030-future-scenarios>
http://www.ihdp.unu.edu/docs/Publications/GECAFS/GECAFS_Report_2_Caribbean_Scenarios.pdf

2.4 STEP 4 - CLIMATE POLICY Pathway – Global to local

Responsible partners: WP7 will provide the template for compilation of information on policies. IFPs will compile the information for national or regional (island-level) policies. WP7 will compile the information at EU level and IFPs will compile the information for each island region or country.

Links to other work packages: Under definition

This step will be implemented in D7.2/T7.2 and D7.3/T7.3 and will considered the outputs provided by WP5.

STEP 4.1 - Compile climate policy options at European level. The aim of this exercise is to identify objectives and targets of policies, evaluating how climate change may assist or prevent the achievement of these targets³:

STEP 4.1a - Compile EU “Climate Policy Goals”

STEP 4.1b - Compile EU “Policy Regimes and Measures”

STEP 4.1c - Compile EU “Implementation Limits and Obstacles” (Kriegler *et al.*, 2014)

STEP 4.2: Compile climate policy options at island (national or regional) level. The aim of this policy review is to identify objectives and targets of policies to evaluate how climate change may assist or prevent the achievement of these targets (this Step is already partially achieved - see chapter **Error! Reference source not found.**)⁴.

STEP 4.2a - Compile island “Climate Policy Goals”

STEP 4.2b - Compile island “Policy Regimes and Measures”

STEP 4.2c - Compile island “Implementation Limits and Obstacles” (Kriegler *et al.*, 2014)

STEP 4.3 - Design a survey to collect island climate policies (to be used as the basis for a set of shared climate policy assumptions). The IFP and sectors expert partners will be consulted and will provide validation of the policy context.

STEP 4.4 – Compare climate and sectoral policies according to a set of pre-defined criteria and consider their time dependency (provide input for STEP 6). The criteria **create and evaluate** Adaptation tradeoffs with Mitigation

³ Just the existing goals, regimes and limits/obstacles

⁴ The islands will have climate change adaptation or disaster risk management plans which will be included here.

2.4.1 Use of SPAs at the Island level

For the work to be developed, the policies screened at Island level will fit in the concept of shared policy assumptions (SPA). The SPA definition used follows Kriegler et al. 2014 and captures key elements of climate policies considering their geographical application and time dependency. Also, policies that are different from the global tendencies and that strongly influence local vulnerability and climate-related risks will be considered.

To connect the socioeconomic context with climate we will need to map the assumptions about adaptation and disaster risk reduction (DRR) policies. The climate change policy (adaptation or DRR) efforts within a socioeconomic SSP will be based on the current approach of *Shared Policy Assumptions* (SPA).

A screening of climate policies related with adaptation is proposed to be performed at two different levels of decision-making: (1) EU and (2) Island/ region. In this context the current and future climate-related policies, DRR or general policies that could influence climate actions should be included. At this stage (1) will bring structure to the policy and (2) will add the specific characteristics of the island that are object of study.

The method proposed to screen climate policies aims to create better conditions to connect the socio-economic scenarios with climate change future risks. It also assumes that those scenarios are crucial to anticipate and measure climate change risks, and need to include information about climate, society and economy.

The policies inventory will support the creation of a policy option at EU and Islands level (used in Step 5 and 6). To collect the four levels of policy: European, national, regional and sectoral, it will be necessary to consider (by priority order):

- European scale defines the policy base in the member states. The documents that could be considered are: (1) Adaptation: EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change; (2) Disaster Risk Reduction: EU Civil Protection Mechanism;

For implementing the conceptual framework in SOCLIMPACT, it is relevant to consider the link between climate risk and adaptation in the European context. The EU Action Plan on the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction and the national, regional and local derivatives, if any, will also be considered to develop the shared policy assumptions.

- National scale (Malta and Cyprus): (1) Adaptation: National adaptation strategy (NAS) and national and/or sectoral adaptation plans (NAP/SAP) in place; (2) Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs); (3) Disaster Risk Reduction Plans
- Regional/Island scale: (1) Adaptation: Regional adaptation strategy or program; Local relevant Sectorial plans programs of strategies; Transport (to define Maritime Transport policy in adaptation context); Tourism (to define Coastal and Maritime Tourism policy in adaptation context); Aquaculture and fisheries (to define Aquaculture policy in adaptation context); Energy (to define Energy policy in adaptation context); (3) In some cases, the Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs); (4) Relevant Islands context initiatives: - Clean Energy Initiative for Islands (energy); - Smart Islands

Initiative - Clean energy transition on EU islands and beyond; (5) Disaster Prevention and Preparedness plans.

Box 1.4: Whale watching case study: Example of step 5

- The screening of policies for tourism and whale watching at different scales will be carried out and a compilation of policy goals and measures will be obtained.
- Current policies will be assessed according to the different pathway alternatives. Barriers to accomplish policy goals will be identified and proposals for alternative measures will be discussed in stakeholder workshops to provide solutions under the different proposed pathways.

2.5 STEP 5 - ALTERNATIVE Pathways (Climate, Socio-economy and climate policy)

This step will be implemented in D7.3/T7.3 and revised in D7.4/T7.4 will considered the outputs created on: Step 1 - risk pathway, Step 2 - climate pathway, Step 3 - socio-economic pathway and step 4 - climate policy pathway.

Task 5.1 - Combined SSP storylines and RCPs, inside which will be created a coherent policy pathway using SSP-RCP scenario matrix based on Step 2 (WP4 using a RCP model) and Step 3 (WP6 using SSP2 basic elements input). This matrix will indicate the combination of socioeconomic development pathway (SSP) and climate outcome based on coherent pathway forcing (RCP) (Riahi *et al.*, 2017).

Table 4 - RCPs and SSPs matrix combination in SOCLIMPACT and coherent scenario

		Shared Socioeconomic Pathways				
		SSP1	SSP2	SSP3	SSP4	SSP5
2100 forcing level (W m ⁻²)	RCP 8.5					
	RCP 7.0					
	RCP 6.0					
	RCP 4.5					
	RCP 3.4					
	RCP 2.6					
	RCP 1.9					

Legend:

	Non coherent scenario (Riahi <i>et al.</i> , 2017).
	Coherent scenario (Riahi <i>et al.</i> , 2017)
	Modelled only for Social-economy (in SOCLIMPACT)
	Modelled only for Climate (in SOCLIMPACT)
	Modelled for Social-economy and Climate (in SOCLIMPACT)
	Socioeconomic storylines (WP7) and Climate (in SOCLIMPACT)

Task 5.2 – Organize alternative pathways considering “packages” of adaptation and risk management options for each island.

Task 5.3 – Develop criteria to evaluate the adaptation options, with a different set of criteria per sector in Multi-criteria Analysis (MCA).

2.5.1 Use of RPC-SSP-SPA scenarios

The approach promoted in SOCLIMPACT was derived from the IPCC framework for climate risk and policy assessment that was applied in the Fifth Assessment Report (AR5) (see details in chapter **Error! Reference source not found.**). The IPCC Working Group III team developed a sophisticated methodology, which includes three components:

- Representative Concentration Scenarios (RCPs), which represent the evolution towards different levels of radiative forcing (measured in W/m^2 that comes as a result of the increase in the concentration of CO_2 -equivalent in volume (parts per million) in the atmosphere), which is linked with different levels of global average temperature change. This layer is mainly implemented in STEP 2 using results of WP4.
- The Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP), pathways of economic and social change, organized according to two dimensions: socio-economic challenges to mitigation and adaptation. This layer is mainly developed in STEP 3.
- Shared Policy Assumptions (SPA), which determine a set of assumptions about climate policy and other aspects of the political response to climate change. This layer is mainly developed in STEP 4.

This approach can generically be applied to the climate change policy mitigation, adaptation and disaster risk reduction in the context of the main drivers of change: future climate and socioeconomic conditions.

Box 1.5: Whale watching case study: Example of step 4 application

- The definition of adaptation pathways will be carried out mainly through the combination of the following SSPs (WP7) and RCPs (WP4)
- The four alternative pathways for the whale watching activity will be presented and validated in stakeholder workshops in the respective islands and adaptation and mitigation options will be identified to address the key elements presented in each pathway.

To organize and decide about the future climate change policy options that will be considered, it is proposed that distinct policy trajectories are considered with a realistic outlook to address the projected climatic and socio-economic changes.

The adaptation policy trajectories will follow the scenario matrix architecture used in the DECCMA study (Kay *et al.*, 2018) which explores different levels of (1) commitment to policy change; and (2) investment. Four different policy trajectories are defined:

- A. Minimum Intervention
- B. Economic Capacity Expansion
- C. System Efficiency Enhancement
- D. System Restructuring

2.6 STEP 6 - Engage islands' STAKEHOLDERS - develop adaptation pathways

Responsible partners: Sectors Leaders and IFP

Links to other work packages: input from WP4, WP5 and WP6

This step will be implemented in D7.3/T7.3 and it will consider will considered the outputs provided by WP4 and WP5.

Having defined the baseline policy scenarios in STEP 4 there will be a four-stage participatory approach to define the island policy pathways:

Task 6.1 – Develop the Draft Agenda for the Local Working Group Workshop.

Task 6.2 – Develop a methodology with associated criteria and indicators for multicriteria analysis of the adaptation (with DRR) pathways:

Task 6.2a - Project context guidance.

Task 6.2b – Present the Climate change projections and Hazards for the Island - main Impacts and Risks (from D4.5).

Task 6.2c – Organize round tables discussion for risk and adaptation for each sector considered for the island.

Task 6.2d - Stakeholders will validate and rank pathways and identify actions which will contribute to the achievement of the policy goals identified.

Task 6.2e – Organize and communicate plenary discussions to define adaptation pathway. Summarize the main conclusions of the workshop and define the next steps.

Figure 8 - STEP 6 example - Blue Economy Sectors round tables

Task 6.3 – Create a calendar for workshop considering the IFP and information availability

Workshops calendar		2020									
Partner	Island	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	
FCIENCIAS.ID	Azores										
ANCI	Sardegna										
KRITI	Crete										
ABT	Malta										
ULPGC	Canary Islands										
TEC	Corsica										
AREAM	Madeira										
INTERFUSION	Cyprus										
OTIE	Sicilia										
BEF Germany	Fehmarn										
UA	West Indies										
UIB	Balearic Islands										

Figure 9 – STEP6- workshops calendar example (which is tentative at this stage)

Task 6.4 – Report the result of the workshop (still in D7.3). The stakeholders’ perspective and views on the development of the adaptation pathways/options will be explained. The main question to be answered is how participants are likely to address the risks of climate change projected until 2100.

Figure 10 - STEP 6 example – Potential material to be used in LWG workshops. On the left the pathway to carbon neutrality for Portugal up to 2050 and on the right an example of an adaptation measure having in it several criteria

2.6.1 Notes on participatory process

Together with stakeholders and using the outcomes of the previous steps as input, narratives will be created and used to identify adaptation options suitable for the specific challenges of the

SOCLIMPACT islands.⁵ Conditional trajectories will be created describing when and under which conditions these options can be implemented.

This STEP will be developed in detail in D7.3. Engage islands' stakeholders in the design of alternative pathways. The current document aims to introduce this methodologic step.

The framework created will incorporate the participation of the following stakeholders:

- Island Focal Points (IFPs);
- Local Working Groups (LWGs);
- General Stakeholders;
- Sector partners (inside the project).

Different events or meeting will be organized to optimize the results of the approach, according to the different aims and stakeholders' profiles:

- Online meetings;
- Physical meetings (in context of Sector Modeling Teams or WP7);
- Surveys;
- Workshops (1 per Island).

The interaction with the stakeholders will be focused on the validation and evaluation of the adaptation and DRR pathways and definition of measures.

This methodology step will also be useful to collect and prepare the basis for the next WP7 tasks:

- Informed policy to adapt the EU island;
- Creation of a policy advice reference study;
- Identification of uncertainties applied to policy making in the specific context of EU Islands;
- Characterization of the future role for policy and research to achieve a strong science-policy interface.

⁵ The previous steps will provide a database with generic options that will then together with stakeholders be further finetuned and elaborated for each island

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2.7 STEP 7 - Elaboration of specifications for a common framework for the governance of Blue Economy sectors

This step will organize and considered the output developed in SOCLIMPACT and will be implemented in D7.5/T7.5.

STEP 7.1 – Create a common system Climate Change indicator of impacts (biophysical and socioeconomic) on Blue Economy activities.

STEP 7.2 – Create a dashboard fed by indicators and modelling tools to support decision making.

STEP 7.3 – Merge the adaptation pathways for Blue Economy activities through.

STEP 7.4 – Public guide for a common framework on: (1) governance of Blue Economy Sectors in Islands; (2) lessons learned in SOCLIMPACT project and knowledge gaps; (3) sectors networking and exchange of information beyond the project lifetime.

3 The RPC-SSP-SPA frame of reference

To frame and define a common starting point for different sectors or scales the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change's Fifth Assessment Report (IPCC-AR5) used RCPs that express atmosphere starting conditions for the climate changes models, SSPs that put together predefined packages of socioeconomic future contexts, and SPAs which include: (1) climate policy goals; (2) policy regimes and measures; and (3) implementation limits and obstacle (Kriegler *et al.*, 2014).⁶

A pathway (SSP or RCP) should be combined with Shared Policy Assumptions (SPA) to form an integrated climate scenario. In this context the SSP-RCP-SPA scenario matrix (like the one in Table 4 but for each island) will be created under the context of Scenario MIP simulations (O'Neill *et al.*, 2016):

- Once RCP and SSP scenario combinations will have been selected (for a given island), the time horizons and steps will be considered for all the components (socio-economic, climate and risk), characterizing the systems under investigation;
- All "layers" of information created, which support the scenario framework development at the Island/Archipelago scale, should at this stage contribute the development of the boundary conditions for adaptation and DRR policy pathways;
- Also, the factors that founds each IC (hazard, adaptative capacity, sensibility and exposure) will be used to define the conditions for policy application.

There are multiple factors that have the potential to affect the future socio-economic, biophysical or risk conditions which will be defined under each scenario and the inputs from Impact Chain risk indicators, when possible.

It is recommended that the workshops organized in the context of SOCLIMPACT have the stakeholders and sectoral experts collaborate to develop, test, and validate the adaptation and DRR policy trajectories for each regional context.

3.1 RCP - Climate Hazard and Impacts

The representative concentration pathways (RCP) are the component of the scenarios composed by the emissions produced in the past and for the future and that can be translated into impacts in human and natural systems. This radiative forcing is one of many interfaces between the drivers of climate change (socio-economic drivers and greenhouse gas emissions) and the effective climate change effects (impacts and risks). The RCPs are incorporated in the climate models to define a very wide range of climate futures.

⁶ A global climate scenario toolkit was developed (Ebi *et al.*, 2013, Kriegler *et al.*, 2013, O'Neill *et al.*, 2013, van Vuuren *et al.*, 2013) to provide a typology of alternative futures, and that has enabled systematic exploration of adaptation and mitigation challenges arising from alternative socio-economic futures for different climate scenarios (O'Neill *et al.*, 2017, Riahi *et al.*, 2017).

The selection process to identify the RCPs considered criteria that expressed the needs of the climate scenario developers and users (van Vuuren *et al.*, 2011). Each RCP represents a larger set of scenarios in the literature which are compatible with the full range of emissions scenarios available in the current scientific literature.

The RCPs are consistent sets of projections of radiative forcing in the atmosphere and from where uncertainties about socioeconomic, climate, and impact futures can be explored consistently across different research fields.

The IPCC fifth Assessment Report (AR5) considered four pathways by 2100: RCP2.6, RCP4.5, RCP6 and RCP8.5. However, to cover an even broader range of climates outcomes have been considered more RCPs. In SOCLIMPACT mainly two RCPs were used: RCP2.6 and RCP8.5. This selection is related with the fact that RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 are the most used and published and the RCP2.6 is consistent with keeping warming below 2°C relative to pre-industrial ("likely").⁷

Individually RCPs are described as follows:

- RCP 2.6: developed by the IMAGE modeling team of the Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency. The emission pathway is representative for scenarios in the literature leading to **very low greenhouse gas concentration levels**. It is a so-called "peak" scenario: its radiative forcing level first reaches a value around 3.1 W/m² mid-century, returning to 2.6 W/m² by 2100. In order to reach such radiative forcing levels, greenhouse gas emissions (and indirectly emissions of air pollutants) are reduced substantially over time. The final RCP is based on the publication by Van Vuuren et al. (2007).⁸
- RCP 4.5: developed by the MiniCAM modeling team at the Pacific Northwest National Laboratory's Joint Global Change Research Institute (JGCRI). It is a **stabilization scenario where total radiative forcing is stabilized before 2100** by employment of a range of technologies and strategies for reducing greenhouse gas emissions. The scenario drivers and technology options are detailed in Clarke et al. (2007). Additional detail on the simulation of land use and terrestrial carbon emissions is given by Wise et al (2009).⁹
- RCP 8.5: developed by the MESSAGE modeling team and the IIASA Integrated Assessment Framework at the International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), Austria. The RCP 8.5 is characterized by **increasing greenhouse gas emissions over time representative for scenarios in the literature leading to high greenhouse gas concentration levels**. The underlying scenario drivers and resulting development path are based on the A2r scenario detailed in Riahi et al. (2007).¹⁰

The RCP8.5 represents the 90th percentile of the reference emissions range, while RCP2.6 represents pathways below the 10th percentile of mitigation scenarios.

Table 5 – The three RCPs commonly used for research (Weyant et al., 2010)

⁷ see AR5, summary for policy makers, table SPM.2, page 21: RCP4.5 has an average of 1.8°C at the end of the century, with a likely range of 1.1°C to 2.6°C

⁸ <http://www.iiasa.ac.at/web-apps/tnt/RcpDb/dsd?Action=htmlpage&page=welcome>

⁹ <http://www.iiasa.ac.at/web-apps/tnt/RcpDb/dsd?Action=htmlpage&page=welcome>

¹⁰ «For example, RCP8.5 cannot be used as a no-climate-policy reference scenario for the other RCPs because RCP8.5's socioeconomic, technology and biophysical assumptions differ from those of the other RCPs» (Riahi et al., 2017)

Name	Radiative forcing	Concentration (ppm)	Pathway	Model providing RCP
RCP8.5	>8.5Wm ⁻² in 2100	1,370 CO ₂ -equiv. in 2100	Rising	MESSAGE
RCP4.5	4.5Wm ⁻² at stabilization after 2100	650 CO ₂ -equiv. (at stabilization after 2100)	Stabilization without overshoot	GCAM
RCP2.6	Peak at 3 Wm ⁻² before 2100 and then declines	Peak at, 490 CO ₂ -equiv. before 2100 and then declines	Peak and decline	IMAGE

Figure 11 – Query results as chart preview of global total radiative forcing for historic values from 1950 and projected for RCP8.5, RCP4.5 RCP2.6. Generated from RCP Database

Figure 12 – Query results as chart preview of global CO₂ equivalent concentration for historic from 1950 and projected for RCP8.5, RCP4.5 RCP2.6. Generated from RCP Database (version 2.0.5)

The RCPs will be combined with the SSPs. However, not all SSPs are compatible with the RCPs nor with limiting warming to 1.5 °C or 2 °C above pre-industrial levels.

The development of the RCP pathways, such as the 2.6, 4.5 and 8.5 watt per meter square, intentionally don't include socioeconomic “narratives”, which are the subject of the SSPs.

3.2 SSP – Socio-economic for Blue Sectors

The SSPs describe development in human systems and activities (or sectors) that can be related to RCPs in the climate system. This approach introduces socioeconomic information as part of a

parallel scenario development process. The socioeconomic “futures” are usually quantified by *Integrated Assessment Models* (IAMs) to create consistent results for indicators such as population, urbanization, education, and GDP that determine energy consumption, land-use and GHG emissions pathways.

The socio-economic component of SOCLIMPACT Framework aims to integrate the future climate impacts, vulnerabilities, adaptation, and mitigation in a quantitative projection of the socio-economic pathway. Generally, SOCLIMPACT Framework will follow these socioeconomic “narratives” principles that are based on:

- ✓ no climate policy imbedded and considering no global effort to address climate change;
- ✓ define different baseline worlds that might occur;
- ✓ to offer a wide range of future mitigation and adaptation challenges;
- ✓ to be independently combined with RCPs.¹¹

Therefore, the SSPs baseline represents a world without future policies or measures to address climate change however the SSPs are significantly different in how the use of energy will be. This series of outcomes in absence of additional climate policy allows the researchers to study how the policy (SPAs) would fit into the future described by each SSP.

The socio-economic component involves qualitative and quantitative elements that describe the future world in terms of, for example, population, governance, inequality, institutions, technology, and environment (O'Neill *et al.*, 2012; van Vuuren *et al.*, 2014a). This information is commonly used to incorporate the future socio-economic in to assessments which is also the intended in SOCLIMPACT within the WP6 (WP7 will collect some of the assumption use in WP6, to guarantee coherence in the Project).

In SOCLIMPACT storylines with simplified qualitative descriptions of alternative socio-economic pathways for future society will be developed, see **Figure 7** - STEP 3.4 example - Blue Economy Sectors SSPs tendencies and indicators at Island level. Those SSP storylines developed by sector can be translated in the future translated into a quantified output in terms of the main drivers of economic growth already developed for SSP2 in WP6.

The development of SSPs proposed by O'Neill (O'Neill *et al.*, 2014) focuses on two stages – the basic and the extended SSPs. The basic SSPs aim to provide enough detail and comprehensiveness to distinguish between the different storylines framed by the challenges for mitigation and adaptation. In a second stage, where SOCLIMPACT project will start, the aim is to extend the basic SSPs by providing additional qualitative and quantitative information to support specific sectoral and regional analysis. The aim of this two-stage approach was to provide a minimum set of assumptions that could rapidly be available for use by a wide range of research communities enabling regional and sectoral extensions of the basic SSPs. The development and application of

¹¹ Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs), describe different levels of radiative forcing for the future.

extended SSPs are recently being developed aiming to inform decisions at a variety of different scales.

Figure 13 – The “challenges space” to be spanned by SSPs divided into five “domains” with one SSP located within each domain (O’Neill *et al.*, 2014)

The global socioeconomic pathways set alternative futures of societal development known as SSPs and are described by O’Neill (O’Neill *et al.*, 2017; Riahi *et al.*, 2017). The global narratives proposed were structured in five pathways that the world could take:

- SSP1: Sustainability—Taking the green road
- SSP2: “middle of the road” -
- SSP3: Regional rivalry—A rocky road
- SSP4: Inequality—A road divided
- SSP5: Fossil-fueled development—Taking the highway

Generally, the socioeconomic challenges to mitigation could be separated in factors related with the mitigation effort necessary, in other words, the dimension (emissions) of the mitigation task; and factors related with the capacity of a society to mitigate (Kriegler *et al.*, 2014). Mitigation challenges are related with factors like: Population, Carbon intensity, Energy Intensity, Energy-related Technology Change, CCS availability, Effectiveness of Policy Institutions, Energy Technology Transfer and Diet (see Figure 13)

The other axis of challenge is adaptation which is related with the concepts of Exposure, Sensitivity and Adaptive Capacity to a specific Hazard (or RCP). Those concepts and definitions were applied in SOCLIMPACT through the Impact Change methodology and can be translated, for example, in factors like: Average Wealth, Poverty, Governance, Water Availability, Innovation Capacity, Coastal Population, Educational Attainment, Urbanization, Quality of Healthcare and Availability of Insurance (Kriegler *et al.*, 2014) (see Figure 13).

SSPs include quantifications of factors considered drivers, such as population growth and economic growth, but the quantification of the consequences of these factors for the energy system, emissions and climate changes are called scenarios based on the SSPs (van Vuuren *et al.*, 2014b, 2014a)

Thus, this scenario framework distinguishes between pathways, which describe a component (such as RCPs or SSPs) of the integrated "scenarios", which combine pathways with additional information such as emissions, climate and climate impacts projections, and, for mitigation scenarios, climate policy assumptions, to produce integrated descriptions of the future climate and the development of the human system.

The scenarios are defined in different “challenges spaces”, represented by two vectors of challenges: one depicts challenges pertaining to adaptation; the other challenges to mitigation (O’Neill *et al.*, 2014).

The global elements of SSPs define challenges to mitigation and adaptation that can be extended for each region or sector. The elements will be developed in the context of the blue economy sectors and are based in the work of O’Neill *et al.*, 2014 (see **Error! Reference source not found.**).

*Table 6 - Possible elements of SSPs relevant to defining challenges to mitigation and adaptation (O’Neill *et al.*, 2014).*

Scenario element GLOBAL	
Demographics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Population total and age structure • Urban vs. rural populations, and urban forms • Other location information, such as coastal vs. inland
Economic development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Global and regional GDP, or trends in productivity • Regional, national, and sub-national distribution of GDP, including economic catch-up by developing countries • Sectoral structure of national economies, the share of agriculture, and agricultural land productivity • Share of population in extreme poverty • Nature of international trade
Welfare	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Human development • Educational attainment • Health, including access to public health and health care infrastructure
Environmental and ecological factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Air, water, soil quality • Ecosystem functioning
Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fossil fuel resources and renewable energy potentials • Other key resources, such as phosphates, fresh water etc.
Institutions and governance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Existence, type and effectiveness of national/regional/global institutions • Degree of participation • Rule of law
Technological development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Type (e.g. slow, rapid, transformational) and direction (e.g. environmental, efficiency, productivity improving) of technological progress • Diffusion of innovation in particular sectors, e.g. energy supply, distribution and demand, industry, transport, agriculture
Broader societal factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attitudes to environment/sustainability/equity and world views • Life styles (including diets) • Societal tension and conflict levels

Policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-climate policies including development policies, technology policies, urban planning and transportation policies, energy security policies, and environmental policies to protect air, soil and water quality. It is possible that SSPs could be specified partly in terms of policy objectives, such as strong welfare-improving goals, rather than specific policy targets or measures.
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The narratives are usually developed according to several socio-economic elements. These elements are summarized in table 4 for the EU by SSP (Kok and Pedde, 2016):

Table 7 - Possible elements on EU – SSPs (Kok and Pedde, 2016).

Key elements	Eur-SSP1 - We are the World	Eur-SSP3 - Icarus	Eur-SSP4 - Riders on the Storm	Eur-SSP5 - Fossil-fuelled Development
Decision-making level	International/EU leader	National/local widespread fragmentation	International / Europe leader on the global scale	International/EU not a leader on the global scale
International cooperation	Strong, EU important player	Weak	Strong, EU important player	Strong (trade)
Migration	Low immigration	Outmigration	Selected immigration	High to cities and from poorer countries
Economic	Gradual (with hiccups at the beginning)	Low	High	High
Mobility	No barriers, but movements are limited	Low	High	High
Social cohesion	High	Low EU/higher within countries	Low	High
Technology development	High, but not pervasive	Low	High in some areas; low in labor intensive areas	Strong and crucial
Quality of Governance	High—focus on sustainability	Low and ineffective	High and effective	High with focus on businesses
Human health investments	High	Low	High for elites, medium for lower class	High
Education investments	High	Low	High for elites, medium for lower class	High
Environmental respect	High	Low	High in pockets	Low, with high 'not in my backyard'

To develop the socio-economic pathways for the different regions in SOCLIMPACT two socio-economic narratives are available at different scales:

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- (1) Global SSP, (O'Neill et al., 2017)
- (2) EU SSPs (Kok et al., 2018)

Table 8 – Global SSPs (O'Neill et al., 2017) and EU – SSPs (Kok et al., 2018) Narratives or storylines.

	Global (O'Neill et al., 2017)	EU (Kok et al., 2018)
SSP1	<p>SSP1: Sustainability—Taking the green road</p> <p>The world shifts gradually, but pervasively, toward a more sustainable path, emphasizing more inclusive development that respects perceived environmental boundaries. Increasing evidence of and accounting for the social, cultural, and economic costs of environmental degradation and inequality drive this shift. Management of the global commons slowly improves, facilitated by increasingly effective and persistent cooperation and collaboration of local, national, and international organizations and institutions, the private sector, and civil society. Educational and health investments accelerate the demographic transition, leading to a relatively low population. Beginning with current high-income countries, the emphasis on economic growth shifts toward a broader emphasis on human well-being, even at the expense of somewhat slower economic growth over the longer term. Driven by an increasing commitment to achieving development goals, inequality is reduced both across and within countries. Investment in environmental technology and changes in tax structures lead to improved resource efficiency, reducing overall energy and resource use and improving environmental conditions over the longer term. Increased investment, financial incentives and changing perceptions make renewable energy more attractive. Consumption is oriented toward low material growth and lower resource and energy intensity. The combination of directed development of environmentally friendly technologies, a favorable outlook for renewable energy, institutions that can facilitate international cooperation, and relatively low energy demand results in relatively low challenges to mitigation. At the same time, the improvements in human well-being, along with strong and flexible global, regional, and national institutions imply low challenges to adaptation.</p>	<p>European-shared socio-economic pathway 1 (Eur-SSP1)—We are the World</p> <p>The interplay of financial, environmental, and economic crises fuel the feeling that behaviour has to change away from an unregulated market-driven economy to a sustainable development path. This puts governments under pressure to take ambitious measures, including stimulating an energy transition towards renewables and facilitating innovative research, accompanied by investments in health, education, and social support. A decrease in conflicts in Europe's southern and eastern border regions leads to higher political stability and moderate but steady economic growth in an increasingly equitable Europe. The European Union expands further and participates in new global governance initiatives. Advances in green technologies are further stimulated by international competition leading to a CO2 neutral society by 2050. By 2100, Europe is characterised by a high level of sustainability-oriented political and societal awareness, focusing on renewable energy and low-material growth in a strongly regulated but effective multi-level governance structure.</p>

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SSP2	<p>SSP2: The world follows a path in which social, economic, and technological trends do not shift markedly from historical patterns. Development and income growth proceeds unevenly, with some countries making relatively good progress while others fall short of expectations. Most economies are politically stable. Globally connected markets function imperfectly. Global and national institutions work toward but make slow progress in achieving sustainable development goals, including improved living conditions and access to education, safe water, and health care. Technological development proceeds apace, but without fundamental breakthroughs. Environmental systems experience degradation, although there are some improvements and overall the intensity of resource and energy use declines. Even though fossil fuel dependency decreases slowly, there is no reluctance to use unconventional fossil resources. Global population growth is moderate and levels off in the second half of the century as a consequence of completion of the demographic transition. However, education investments are not high enough to accelerate the transition to low fertility rates in low-income countries and to rapidly slow population growth. This growth, along with income inequality that persists or improves only slowly, continuing societal stratification, and limited social cohesion, maintain challenges to reducing vulnerability to societal and environmental changes and constrain significant advances in sustainable development. These moderate development trends leave the world, on average, facing moderate challenges to mitigation and adaptation, but with significant heterogeneities across and within countries.</p>	<p>Not developed considering the difficulty in developing new SSP2-based stories since almost all elements change moderately.</p>
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SSP3: Regional rivalry—A rocky road

A resurgent nationalism, concerns about competitiveness and security, and regional conflicts push countries to increasingly focus on domestic or, at most, regional issues. This trend is reinforced by the limited number of comparatively weak global institutions, with uneven coordination and cooperation for addressing environmental and other global concerns. Policies shift over time to become increasingly oriented toward national and regional security issues, including barriers to trade, particularly in the energy resource and agricultural markets. Countries focus on achieving energy and food security goals within their own regions at the expense of broader-based development, and in several regions move toward more authoritarian forms of government with highly regulated economies. Investments in education and technological development decline. Economic development is slow, consumption is material-intensive, and inequalities persist or worsen over time, especially in developing countries. There are pockets of extreme poverty alongside pockets of moderate wealth, with many countries struggling to maintain living standards and provide access to safe water, improved sanitation, and health care for disadvantaged populations. A low international priority for addressing environmental concerns leads to strong environmental degradation in some regions. The combination of impeded development and limited environmental concern results in poor progress toward sustainability. Population growth is low in industrialized and high in developing countries. Growing resource intensity and fossil fuel dependency along with difficulty in achieving international cooperation and slow technological change imply high challenges to mitigation. The limited progress on human development, slow income growth, and lack of effective institutions, especially those that can act across regions, implies high challenges to adaptation for many groups in all regions.

SSP3

European-shared socio-economic pathway 3 (Eur-SSP3) — Icarus

With the economy gradually picking up, the demand for resources increases, which turns out to be a tipping point for the state of the environment with severe ecosystem failures. The persistence of conflicts and decline in trade also substantially increases energy and food prices, whilst initiating a massive build-up of the military industry, which is resource hungry but not resource efficient. Long-term policy planning becomes rare with hardly any money for education, research or innovation. Eventually, the EU breaks down, with new regional blocs forming in the north and in the south of Europe, whilst new alliances with other countries are forged to ensure sufficient energy supply. Social countermovements temporarily appear but do not take root in a fragmented and divided Europe with strong regional rivalry and conflict. Ultimately, a high-carbon intensive Europe emerges that is not worse off than the rest of the world, but struggles not to become the world's backwater with high inequalities predominantly between, but also within, countries.

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SSP4: Inequality—A road divided

Highly unequal investments in human capital, combined with increasing disparities in economic opportunity and political power, lead to increasing inequalities and stratification both across and within countries. Over time, a gap widens between an internationally-connected society that is well educated and contributes to knowledge- and capital-intensive sectors of the global economy, and a fragmented collection of lower-income, poorly educated societies that work in a labor intensive, lowtech economy. Power becomes more concentrated in a relatively small political and business elite, even in democratic societies, while vulnerable groups have little representation in national and global institutions. Economic growth is moderate in industrialized and middle-income countries, while low income countries lag behind, in many cases struggling to provide adequate access to water, sanitation and health care for the poor. Social cohesion degrades and conflict and unrest become increasingly common. Technology development is high in the high-tech economy and sectors. Uncertainty in the fossil fuel markets lead to underinvestment in new resources in many regions of the world. Energy companies hedge against price fluctuations partly through diversifying their energy sources, with investments in both carbon-intensive fuels like coal and unconventional oil, but also low-carbon energy sources. Environmental policies focus on local issues around middle and high income areas. The combination of some development of low carbon supply options and expertise, and a well-integrated international political and business class capable of acting quickly and decisively, implies low challenges to mitigation. Challenges to adaptation are high for the substantial proportions of populations at low levels of development and with limited access to effective institutions for coping with economic or environmental stresses.

European-shared socio-economic pathway 4 (Eur-SSP4) — Riders on the Storm

Sparked by economic crisis and extreme weather events, the EU increases commitment to find innovative solutions to the depletion of natural resources and climate change. In combination with current relatively high levels of social cohesion, energy efficiency, and environmental policy making this initiates a shift towards a high-tech green Europe. This transformation is strongly supported by large businesses that successfully seek collaboration with the increasingly powerful European government. At the same time, however, inequalities are rising because of a number of simultaneously acting factors, including highly unequal investments in education. This leads to a large and widening gap between an internationally connected society and a more fragmented collection of lower income societies that work in a labour intensive, lowtech economy. Technological development has not resulted in reduced energy prices, but has instead established an oligarchy of green business developers that control energy supply. By 2100, Europe is relatively strong, but with growing inequalities across and within European countries.

SSP4

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SSP5: Fossil-fueled development—Taking the highway

Driven by the economic success of industrialized and emerging economies, this world places increasing faith in competitive markets, innovation and participatory societies to produce rapid technological progress and development of human capital as the path to sustainable development. Global markets are increasingly integrated, with interventions focused on maintaining competition and removing institutional barriers to the participation of disadvantaged population groups. There are also strong investments in health, education, and institutions to enhance human and social capital. At the same time, the push for economic and social development is coupled with the exploitation of abundant fossil fuel resources and the adoption of resource and energy intensive lifestyles around the world. All these factors lead to rapid growth of the global economy. There is faith in the ability to effectively manage social and ecological systems, including by geo-engineering if necessary. While local environmental impacts are addressed effectively by technological solutions, there is relatively little effort to avoid potential global environmental impacts due to a perceived tradeoff with progress on economic development. Global population peaks and declines in the 21st century. Though fertility declines rapidly in developing countries, fertility levels in high income countries are relatively high (at or above replacement level) due to optimistic economic outlooks. International mobility is increased by gradually opening up labor markets as income disparities decrease. The strong reliance on fossil fuels and the lack of global environmental concern result in potentially high challenges to mitigation. The attainment of human development goals, robust economic growth, and highly engineered infrastructure results in relatively low challenges to adaptation to any potential climate change for all but a few.

SSP5

European-shared socio-economic pathway 5 (Eur-SSP5) — Fossil-fueled Development

Global markets are increasingly integrated, with interventions focused on removing institutional barriers. There are also strong investments in health, education, and institutions to enhance human and social capital. The push for economic and social development is coupled with the exploitation of abundant fossil fuel resources, including large-scale extraction of shale gas. This further stimulates economic wealth, part of which is used to stimulate the development of (green) technologies. Europe regains its leading position in the global economy. Faith is strong in the ability to effectively manage social and ecological systems, including by geo-engineering. Population across all societal classes adopts a very energy intensive lifestyle. The environment degrades, but the majority of the population is unaware because of successful technological innovation. Towards 2100, the environment is locally seriously degraded as non-renewables are further exploited, which eventually results in a slow re-emergence of investments in renewables.

3.2.1 SSPs application overview

In this section we provide an overview of the SSPs relevant for SOCLIMPACT regarding the geographical scale, i.e., regions or islands considered in the project, as well as the EU Blue Economy Sectors and related ocean scenarios.

Five Oceanic System Pathways (OSPs) were developed based on the five global SSPs focusing on long-term storylines for open ocean fisheries. These aim to provide long term scenarios for fisheries management, which are usually based on the present condition of fish stocks and short-term projections of fisheries catches (Maury *et al.*, 2017). These pathways are expected to serve as tools to assist decision-making by framing long-term goals to support present day management decisions. The five OSPs were developed considering three domains - economy, governance and management. For each domain key driving forces were identified, and assumptions were made for each OSP. The key drivers were wild fish demand and fishing cost market (Economy domain); institutions, corporate influence and convergence (Governance and Geopolitics domain) and objectives, compliance and tools (Management domain). Further research aims to quantify the key drivers described in each OSP to be used in coupled socio-ecological models.

Mullon *et al.* (2016) provided a modeling framework for the North Atlantic fisheries, quantifying pathways based on climate, ecological–economic and governance modelling scenarios until 2040. The scenarios investigate the effects of climate change and economic processes in the social–ecological North Atlantic fisheries system. Results showed a poleward latitudinal shift of species ranges for all emission scenarios; that the effects of governance and trade decisions are more relevant for an outcome than climate change effects; and that the level of fisheries regulation is the most important factor for the evolution of the fisheries system in addition to the interplay between wild fisheries and aquaculture. Scenarios highlighted the variability of fleet profits and the volatile state of fisheries industries in the long term.

Regional extensions of SSPs were developed for the Baltic Sea region exploring long-term environmental problems by identifying regional pressures and elaborating assumptions for the five different regional SSPs (Olesen *et al.*, 2019). The approach to extending SSPs was two-staged, first the identification of primary regional drivers that were regionalized versions of the global drivers which drive the development of regional sectors (general social trends) and a second stage in which secondary drivers were explored, consisting of pressures and activities that could lead to state changes in the Baltic Sea (e.g. eutrophication, risks of marine traffic and biodiversity specifically fish and fisheries).

For the Mediterranean coastal zone SSPs were developed based on global scale SSP narratives developed by Merkens *et al.*, 2016 (Reimann, Merkens and Vafeidis, 2018) which focus on the degree of human settlements in the coastal zone. The elements identified by Merkens *et al.* (2016) (shipping, fisheries, coastal tourism, lifestyle migration and coastal zone management) served as basis for narrative development and were extended for the Mediterranean considering its specific elements of coastal socio-economic development (Reimann, Merkens and Vafeidis, 2018). In addition, regions in the Mediterranean were differentiated between northern, eastern and southern countries due to differences in their current state of socio-economic development. Each Mediterranean SSP is quantified by population growth rates which show an increase across all SSPs until 2100 except for SSP1 where population declines. However, considerable differences were observed between geographic regions and countries.

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In addition to the regional extensions, sectoral pathways were developed for Fisheries and Aquaculture in Europe (CERES, 2016). Four socio-political scenarios were created with quantitative information at the country level and are available in the IIASA database ([SSP Database - IIASA](#)). This database includes projections of population, urban population, education and GDP per capita. Based on this information, draft socio-political storylines were elaborated for fisheries and aquaculture for Europe (CERES, 2016).

Other studies focusing on future ocean scenarios have applied different methodologies for scenario development, aiming to broaden the capacity of exploring complex socio-ecological futures in dedicated narratives (Merrie et al., 2018). Additionally, studies focusing on global environmental assessments have made use of scenarios to explore how different pathways of human development and policy choices have an impact on nature and biodiversity loss (Rosa *et al.*, 2017).

Regional SSPs extensions such as for the Baltic Sea and for the Mediterranean coastal areas, will be harmonized with the sectoral SSPs developed in SOCLIMPACT. In SOCLIMPACT, the regional extensions will be considered, and the drivers identified in each region will inform the development of SSPs for each sector and island and allow comparability across these different studies. Also, international scenarios in tourism sector can be considered.¹²

¹²

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0261517786900555>

<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/pdf/10.1080/02508281.2015.1075739>

<https://www.etfi.nl/en/projects/sustainable-tourism-2040>

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/253920784_Mediterranean_Tourism_Exploring_the_Future_with_the_Tourism_Climatic_Index

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3.3 SPA - Islands Climate Change Policy

The SPAs (Shared climate Policy Assumptions) are one of the components for the framework to create scenarios where policy attributes such as the goals, instruments and obstacles should fit. In SOCLIMPACT we will identify and characterize policy using Kriegler *et al.*, 2014 and using there different items: “Climate Policy Goals”, “Policy Regimes and Measures” and “Implementation Limits and Obstacles”.

3.3.1 Climate Change Policy Global to Islands

According to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), climate change is unequivocal and the continued emission of greenhouse gases will increase the probability of significant changes in the climate system with severe and irreversible impacts which can lead to great socioeconomic and ecological effects (Scott, Hall and Gössling, 2016).

Since 2015, for mitigation of GHG emissions, climate policies are framed by the implementation of the Paris Agreement, which has enhanced interest in low-emission scenarios across the world. EU Member States have all submitted plans to reduce emissions in so-called Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs), which cover EU island Member States (Cyprus, Malta) but also islands in the territories of the other Member States which are covered by SOCLIMPACT. Current NDCs are not only voluntary, but also insufficient to reach the goals (UNEP, 2018). Thus, even if the climate goals of the Paris Agreement would be reached, residual impacts will not be avoided. Therefore, the formulation of climate change response options and measures should not only promote pathways of decarbonizing the economy in an efficient way but also enhance resilience to adverse climate impacts.

Commitment of the European Union on climate change mitigation has been strong since the 1997 Kyoto agreement, with successive and ever more ambitious greenhouse gas emissions reduction targets. This culminated in the “strategic long-term vision for a prosperous, modern, competitive and climate-neutral economy by 2050”. The objective is to achieve “(...) net-zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2050 through a socially-fair transition in a cost-efficient manner.” However, “the proposed Strategy does not intend to launch new policies, nor does the European Commission intend to revise 2030 targets”, but rather to lay down the foundations for the Paris Agreement and in line with UN Sustainable Development Goals. (European Commission, 2018a).

The policy framework for climate and energy in the period from 2020 to 2030 (European Commission, 2014) includes key targets for 2030:

- At least 40% cuts in greenhouse gas emissions (from 1990 levels);
- At least 32% share for renewable energy;
- At least 32.5% improvement in energy efficiency.

These will be achieved using several mechanisms like the EU emissions trading system (ETS), member states commitments, investment support in efficiency, better governance system, National Climate and Energy Plans (NECPs) and National long-term strategies (adapted from European Commission, 2019).

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In the field of adaptation to climate change, policy makers require detailed and precise information about the likelihood and dimension of the impacts (Capela Lourenço, 2015). Adaptation to climate change impacts should be focused on the decision, which implies evaluation, planning and implementation of adaptation options (Füssel, 2007), depending on the conditions and background of each sector and location. It is recognized that integrated complementary approaches need to be developed, which can benefit from the input of stakeholders at different times, setting critical thresholds for specific climate change vulnerabilities (Adger, Arnell and Tompkins, 2005).

The integration of long temporal and large spatial scales in adaptation is a challenge that needs to be integrated into the rational of governance practices. Adaptation can be based on uncoordinated, *ad hoc* choices and actions of individuals and different stakeholders, or based on collective choices, coordinating numerous actions at various levels - local, regional, national or supranational (Swart *et al.*, 2009). Adaptation requires multidisciplinary knowledge, shared responsibility and actions coordinated between different governmental and non-governmental actors in different policy areas (Venturini, 2014). However, most national adaptation policies do not explicitly specify the roles and responsibilities of lower levels of governance in the process of adaptation (Biesbroek *et al.*, 2010).

The EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change recognizes the outermost regions of the EU as particularly vulnerable to the impacts of climate change. These regions are characterized by their insularity, climate and biodiversity richness, as well as economic dependence on a limited number of economic activities or products, such as tourism or fishing (Sauter *et al.*, 2013). They are also heavily dependent on imported oil to cover their energy needs, especially regarding power generation and road transport. In the case of electricity, increase demand can be expected from rising temperatures due to air-conditioning needs.

The EU strategy on adaptation to climate change (2013) has three specific goals, with eight individual actions which can be considered more relevant to the energy sector: Encourage all Member States to adopt comprehensive adaptation strategies; Introduce adaptation in the Covenant of Mayors; Bridge the knowledge gap; Ensure more resilient infrastructure. Currently 25 member states have National Adaptation Strategies that allow for the funding of adaptation related investments. The Covenant of Mayors, initially intended for EU climate and energy targets (related with mitigation), is now “(...) covering 60 million inhabitants, had committed to conduct vulnerability and risk assessments, and to develop, implement and report on adaptation plans.” To bridge the knowledge gap there has been “(...) a substantial increase of adaptation knowledge (...)”, but “uncertainty, however, can be integrated in modelling, transparent and open decision-making; it is no excuse for inaction.” To ensure more resilient infrastructure efforts were developed but it was considered that “there is room to further expand the integration of adaptation in infrastructure, e.g. by prescribing climate proofing for any infrastructure funded by the EU, and particularly when the infrastructure is vital for emission reduction efforts.” (Commission, 2018).

EU - Adaptation Policy structure			
Aim	Priority (P)	Actions (A)	Implementation
"Making Europe more climate-resilient; coordination and information-sharing; relevancy for EU policies and funding programmes"	P1 - Promoting action by Member States	A1 - Adaptation Strategies and Action Plans	MS Adaptation Preparedness Scoreboard: Portugal (Azores, Madeira); Spain (Canaries, Balearic); France (Corseca, West Indies); Italy (Sardiane Silily); Greece (Create); Cyprus; Malta; Germany (Fehman)
		A2 - LIFE funding, including adaptation priority areas	EU Floods Directive trans-boundary coastal management; urban land use planning, building layouts and natural resources management mountain and island areas; agricultural, forestry and tourism sectors sustainable management of water; desertification and forest fires; innovative adaptation technologies vulnerability assessments and adaptation strategies
		A3 - Adaptation Action: cities through the Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy initiative	Adaptation Strategies; Baseline - Risk and Vulnerability Assessment: (1) Status in the adaptation cycle (preparing the ground, assessing risk and vulnerabilities, identify & Select adaptation options, implementing, monitoring and evaluating); (2) Risk rating matrix - Risk level, intensity, frequency time scaled (Droughts, Extreme Cold, Extreme Heat, Extreme Precipitation, Forest Fires, Landslides, Sea Level Rise, Storms); (3) Impact rating Matrix - Impact level, Occurrence Likelihood (by sector: Buildings, Transport, Energy, Water, Waste, Water, Land Use Planning, Agriculture & Forestry, Environment & Biodiversity, Health, Civil Protection & Emergency, Tourism)
	P2 - Better informed decision-making	A4 - Knowledge-gap strategy	Projection of economic impacts of climate change (PESETA III); Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S); Climate-ADAPT; Horizon 2020;
		A5 - Climate-ADAPT	Expected climate change in Europe; Current and future vulnerability of regions and sectors; National and transnational adaptation strategies; Adaptation case studies and potential adaptation options; Tools that support adaptation planning
	P3 - key vulnerable sectors	A6 - Climate-proofing' action at EU level (common Agricultural Policy, Cohesion Policy, and the Common Fisheries Policy)	(including coastal and marine, health, infrastructure, rural development, etc.); Mainstreaming on Marine, fisheries and coastal areas: Integrated Maritime Policy (and action plan) and Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD); Mainstreaming on Agriculture & forestry: Common Agricultural Policy; also mainstreaming on Water management, Biodiversity (ecosystem services), Health, Disaster risk reduction.
		A7 - Making Infrastructure more resilient	Mainstreaming adaptation by European Regional Development Fund and Cohesion Fund; "Guidelines on infrastructure and physical assets to climate-proof vulnerable investments"; "Climate Change and Major Projects": https://ec.europa.eu/clima/sites/clima/files/docs/major_projects_en.pdf
		A8 - Promote products & services by insurance and finance markets (against natural and man-made disasters)	

Figure 14 – EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change structure of the objectives by priorities, actions and current implementation.

Addressing climate objectives of European islands is a challenge due to their location and in some case isolation, implication on energy costs, for example, but also because of the needed public support, oriented expertise and funding generating needed to maintain the economic and social development.

Climate change policy pathways also need to consider the allocation of funding for adaptation and the urgency of measuring relevant impacts, especially in vulnerable communities or territories, like islands. Risk-based adaptation planning, based on climate projections, will help mitigate and minimize future risks and damages.

The SOCLIMPACT Islands are European Small States Islands States (Cyprus and Malta), European Baltic and Mediterranean islands (Fehmarn, Balearic Islands, Sicilia, Sardegna, Corsica, Crete, and European Outermost Regions (Azores, Madeira, Canary Islands and French West Indies).

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3.3.2 Blue Economy sectors policy

The term “Blue economy” is used to describe the cross-cutting Blue Growth policy in the context of the EU’s Integrated Maritime Policy. It is a long-term strategy to support sustainable growth in the marine and maritime sectors. In the context of the SOCLIMPACT, this strategic document was used to create the vision for the SOCLIMPACT Blue Economy sectors.

The mainstream of the climate change (adaptation, mitigation and disaster risk reduction) policy in the economic sectors like are relevant for the development of a successful and appropriate option and measures. The climate change policy in the context of the Blue Economy sectors will facilitate climate proofing of Blue Economy sectors and support the development of resilient and adaptive infrastructure to future climate.

The Report on the *Blue Growth Strategy - Towards more sustainable growth and jobs in the blue economy* (European Commission, 2017) highlights long-term challenges for Europe which, among others, considers the: “Global warming and climate change”. Regarding the resources that sustain people, these challenges will lead to tensions that will be particularly focused on food, health, energy, raw materials and water.

In 2012, the Commission elaborated the Blue Growth Strategy (European Commission, 2012, 2017) to support sustainable growth in the marine and maritime sectors as drivers for economic growth, providing solutions for these global long-term challenges.

The strategy focuses on three components: 1) Develop sectors that have a high potential for sustainable jobs and growth (e.g. aquaculture; coastal tourism; marine biotechnology; ocean energy; seabed mining); 2) Provide knowledge, legal certainty and security in the blue economy (e.g. marine knowledge to improve access to information; maritime spatial planning to ensure an efficient and sustainable management of activities at sea and integrated maritime surveillance); 3) Sea basin strategies to ensure tailor-made measures and to foster cooperation between countries.

A set of maritime economic activities related to the marine functions provided by oceans (e.g. maritime transport and shipbuilding, food, nutrition, health and eco-system services, energy and raw materials, leisure, working and living, coastal protection, maritime monitoring and surveillance) were identified and available estimates indicate that GVA (Growth Value Added) of these activities amounts to € 495 bln and the overall employment is estimated at 5.6 bln (Marine KIC Initiative, 2012).

The *Sustainable Growth* and the *Pursued Growth* scenarios are both characterized by strong economic growth, however in the first there are strong environmental commitments and in the second, economic growth develops at the cost of the environment. The *Fragile Recovery* scenario and the *Boom and Burst* scenario are characterized by an unstable growth with a strong environmental awareness in the *Fragile Recovery* scenario and lower environmental awareness with restricted public and private investments in the *Boom and Burst* scenario. In the economic growth scenarios, coastal tourism will increase in northern Europe due to the effects of climate change and a growth in sustainable tourism is envisioned for the *Sustainable Growth* scenario. These scenarios also prospect a flourishing deep (ocean) and short (coastal) shipping sector, investments in aquaculture and in traditional human food production. Investments in offshore wind and ocean renewable energy are envisioned for the “*Sustainable Growth*” and a persisting extraction of oil, gas and minerals for the

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Pursued Growth scenario. A stable or declining cruise shipping sector characterizes the unstable growth scenarios. The *Fragile Recovery* scenario is characterized by a decline in the extraction of oil and gas and an increase in renewables, while the *Boom and Burst* has limited investments for marine monitoring activities. This effort reinforces the need of frame the economic sector in to a scenario development and the need of a strong policy support for the development of Blue Growth sectors.

In sum, Blue Growth is expected to thrive in a scenario of sustainable growth particularly through sustainable maritime innovations. However, the future will depend on the EU's technological and strategic response capacity to drive maritime innovations in a global context (European Commission, 2012). In this context. the project PLAN4BLUE¹³ aims to identify pathways to the sustainable use of sea areas and resources, bringing together key blue growth and maritime spatial planning actors. The project will produce blue growth scenarios for selected economy sectors in the Gulf of Finland, Archipelago Sea, and their coastal areas.

3.3.2.1 *The SOCLIMPACT vision about the Blue Economy sectors*

To develop concrete options for adaptation in islands and to create a rational from the mainstream of the Blue Economy sectors, a review of concepts and references for each sector is made in the next sections of this document. The starting point are the definitions, scope and boundaries of sectors that can be found in D3.1 and D3.2. Here, references will be provided that can be used by IFP to further explore with the hazards and impacts in each sector, which are not developed in other project WPs for their island. Supplementary information about sectors and methodology will be presented in the Annex.

3.3.2.2 *Energy*

The energy system in islands context

The response to reduce **climate change** risks in energy sector needs to be focused not only on generation systems placed in and by the sea, but also on overall electrical infrastructure both at sea and on-land. The **electrical infrastructure** needed to feed power generated in the island is located inland. The whole energy system includes substations, high voltage transmission and distribution grids, conventional fossil back-up power stations, energy storage systems.

In the island context, especially for **non-interconnected** islands, there are other more technical arguments for including also land energy infrastructure in the marine energy analysis. Electricity generation from marine RES systems installed in island surrounding waters, is not a commodity that could be stored, transported over long distances, and sold in overseas markets, but is energy that has to be fed to the island electrical grid, and **consumed in the island**. Marine RES power generation from the supply-side must be balanced at every instant of time with demand-side electricity consumption of the island. This **grid balancing in the island** context is an important technical challenge for non-interconnected island electrical systems, especially in **high RES penetration scenarios**.

¹³ [Maritime Spatial Planning for Sustainable Blue Economies PLAN4BLUE](#)

Conventional fossil back-up generation (installed on-land) is (still) needed to compensate non dispatchable variable and intermittent **RES power generation** (like marine RES), and to guarantee quality and security of energy supply to the island electrical load. On-land **energy storage** infrastructure, although expensive, is crucial to achieve high marine RES penetration in the weak and small island grids. There are electrical **transmission** and **distribution** infrastructure needed to transport power from marine energy devices to energy consumers in the island. Actions are needed to **protect and reduce the vulnerability** of these energy on-land infrastructures, to extreme climate change induced **extreme weather events**.

Climate Change on the demand side

On the demand side, it must be considered that energy has a clear influence on **economic development, health and standard of living** (Jorgenson and Givens, 2015)). Both for people and the economy, the cost of the electricity and its capability to serve human **and business needs** is critical (e.g. thermal comfort using passive heating and cooling integrated with Near Zero Energy Buildings (NZEB) in accordance with Directive (EU) 2018/844 on Energy Performance of Buildings).

Considering thermal comfort in mainland Europe, an **increase of cooling needs** (cooling degree days to compensate for warm weather heat effects) and a **decrease of heating needs** (heating degree days to compensate for cold weather chilling effects) has been observed. Energy use for heating needs has decreased the most (particularly in northern and north-western Europe) but in relative terms cooling needs have risen more (southern and central Europe), (Füssel *et al.*, 2017a). **These tendencies will continue in the future** but the consequences of more frequent and severe heat waves and high temperatures (IPCC, 2014b) will take their toll on morbidity and mortality (Johnson *et al.*, 2005; Robine *et al.*, 2008).

High **energy and peak (power) demand** associated with **high air temperatures** with also increase stresses on electrical energy grids, decreasing efficiency and risk of damages to grid, inconsistencies in energy quality and major power outages (Sathaye, 2011; Zamuda *et al.*, 2013; Füssel *et al.*, 2017a).

The **interactions of the electricity** value chain with other forms of energy should also be considered as outside driving forces, as they also shape the electricity sector. This happens due to **low-carbon mitigation policies**, namely within the context of **electrification of consumption** as the final form of energy (Sugiyama, 2012) or the use of low-carbon heating and cooling processes (Tomescu, 2018), that may do the opposite (e.g. using free cooling systems or adiabatic cooling (water vaporizing mists) instead of electric heat pumps).

Climate Change on the supply side

In the supply side, increased air **temperatures** will reduce the efficiency of the thermodynamic cycle of power plants by increasing the cold source temperature both in conventional fossil fuel and renewable (e.g. Biomass or Geothermal) primary sources of energy. “The higher the heat differential, the higher is the efficiency of conversion and vice versa. As climate change is likely to produce higher air and water temperatures, the heat differential between the machine and the environment will decrease, thus reducing the net power generated from a given amount of (...)” (Mideksa and Kallbekken, 2010) primary energy source. This means that higher air temperatures

will also reduce the power output, either because the thermodynamic cycle becomes shorter, more auxiliary power is needed for cooling or because dissipation of excess heat becomes impossible using standard systems.

Across the globe **precipitation patterns** are changing and will continue to do so in the future (IPCC, 2014b). Some regions will suffer a further decrease in precipitation, which in relative terms can be more significant in the summer months than in yearly total amount (Füssel *et al.*, 2017a). As seen earlier, this may lead to prolonged **shortage** of surface fresh water which will affect some major **thermally driven power plants** but more obviously **hydropower**. “The key resource for hydropower generation is runoff, which is dependent on precipitation”, “(...) although there are other limiting factors”. “In its most accurate form, hydropower-plant based analysis for individual stations gives a better picture of future generation.”(Hamududu and Killingtveit, 2012). **Run-of-the-river** hydroelectric power plants (that may not use dams *per se*), **are more common on islands** mainly due to their smaller size. They tend to be **more sensitive to precipitation fluctuations** than conventional reservoir dams (also known as impoundment facilities), as they do not store water that could be used in the dry season. They rely on the stability of the water flow in basins which in turn depends on precipitation and other factors that may vary in relative proportion, according to the specific landscapes' characteristics and other non-climatic factors.

Occurrence of **heavy precipitation** is a part of the globe's precipitation patterns that is also changing and may continue to change, but it will affect different locations in a different way. **Floods** and **Flash floods** have a negative impact on **hydropower**, where run-of-the-river power may be more susceptible, as they may clog or damage the turbine discharge systems and thus hinder or halt electric production.

Storms may bring **high winds, heavy precipitation, heavy seas (waves) and storm surges**, in combination or separately. **High winds** and heavy **precipitation** are a hazard for all energy infrastructure. Sea **storms** may bring **heavy waves** that may cause permanent damage to low-lying coastal infrastructures. **Sea level rise** will aggravate the effect of **waves** and **storm surges** during storms, favoring more coastal flooding and wave damage to the coastal energy infrastructure, due to the reduction of the effectiveness of man-made and natural protection systems.

The climate impacts on **wind energy resources** and wind power production is not fully understood. For instance, if the **prevailing wind direction** pattern changes in the future, so will productivity in many wind farms, in those which are arranged dependent on the prevailing winds.

Wave and ocean energy rely on ocean wave patterns, sea temperature and salinity that must comply with operational standards in the design phase, but these standards may change over time. Sea storms with **heavy waves** and associated with **storm surges** may impair, damage or destroy infrastructure near coast line and at sea (which in this case includes off-shore wind energy). In specific conditions an increase or decrease of **wave energy potential** was observed depending on the future emission scenarios and location (Reeve *et al.*, 2011).

Sea level rise may render some types of energy infrastructures less productive or even ineffective, if they do not allow for the necessary adaptation in the future. Tidal power plants may be exposed to the effects of **storm surges** and **heavy waves**, which may damage the infrastructure. When located at estuaries or river mouths the occurrence of these events associated with **floods** can make matters worse. The release or the accumulation of sediments must be avoided to ensure the

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continued productivity of the power plant. With some types of wave energy conversion technologies (Drew, Plummer and Sahinkaya, 2009) **sea level rise** may have an impact on productivity, due to the interaction between the technology design and the wave regime change. Wave regime change may occur not only due to wind pattern change at seas (G.P. Harrison and Wallace, 2005) but also due to changes in the sea floor or the interaction with water level on site.

Relevant documents for the sector

Regarding the **assurance of more resilient infrastructure**, “The European Commission in general aims to increase the climate resilience of infrastructure including energy by providing strategical frameworks like the staff working document on “Adapting Infrastructure to Climate Change” (2013) and “Framework Strategy for a Resilient Energy Union with a Forward-Looking Climate Change Policy” (2015)”. (EEA, 2019). The first document is considered “(...) the contribution of the European Union to climate change adaptation in selected infrastructure sectors. It covers energy and transport infrastructure as well as buildings in the EU – sectors (...)” (Climate-ADAPT, 2015). This document is relevant for the design of a suitable **framework** regarding the definition of future policies in **adaptation**, also able to respond to **risk reduction** issues. It encompasses “sector specific impacts” presented previously about the energy sector, the coastal areas and off-shore impacts, outermost regions context and other relevant orientations (that have the potential of turning the final results more in line with the EU policy mainstreaming and financial instruments).

The SOCLIMPACT framework will also facilitate the **contribution** and **benefit** of islanders in regard with the 2030 EU framework targets and strategy, which are totally aligned with the strategic long-term for climate-neutral economy by 2050. This means that the SOCLIMPACT framework on islands will consider adaptation without neglecting the goal to reach **climate-neutral economies** objective, and it assumes that special support should be given to islands achieve such a goal (for instance within the scope of the Clean Energy for Islands Initiative).

For supplementary information about energy and methodology see Annex.

3.3.2.3 Coastal and Maritime Tourism

There is considerable uncertainty about how tourists will respond to the effects of climate change. The research provides details on potential impacts and changes in tourist demand. However, concrete conclusions are difficult to draw since some changes can create opportunities or disruptions in destinations and in related businesses.

The climate change impacts on tourism will imply changes throughout the tourism system: destinations, transit regions and transport systems, tourist-origin regions. Adaptation of the tourism industry is necessary but, in general, it is a significantly less studied sector compared to other sectors (Ford, Berrang-Ford and Paterson, 2011).

The climate plays a significant role in attractiveness of the regions for tourism. For example, in the long term (2100) it is expected that in the southern Mediterranean countries climate conditions can

change tourism revenues by -0.45% 0.31% of GDP per year, depending on the climate scenario and the model considered (Amelung and Moreno, 2009).

The risk related with climate change can be defined as having an impact on the attributes of values of a system and eventually causing yield losses. In tourism sector these attributes can be related with landscapes or the attractiveness of natural heritage.

Since tourist destinations have limited capacity to relocate, their ability to adapt to climate change (adaptive capacity) gets extremely relevant and crucial for regions where the source of income depends heavily on tourism. In addition, a tourism destination aims to remain economically, environmentally and socially sustainable, and in this context the capacity to cope with or minimize potential risks and capitalize on opportunities that arise from climate change is critical.

The research on adaptation of tourism generally falls into the category of "practical application" (Ford, Smit and Wandel, 2006), where the focus is on documenting the different ways in which the system experiences the changes and the means it uses to carry out the process of adaptive decision-making.

Adaptability can be determined by underlying societal factors such as resources, institutions, social and human capital, awareness, information management, participation levels and risk dissemination processes (Pelling, 2011).

The EU strategic document about tourism sector is: *Europe, the world's No 1 tourist destination – a new political framework for tourism in Europe*. This document aims to make an overview of general policy and priority actions. Considering the structural challenges highlighted, the sector considers climate change a strong constraint on the supply (on assets related with water, biodiversity and the cultural heritage) and when measuring the sector responsibility to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and on the potential future restructuring on travel models. One of the actions planned which are related with climate change is the identification climate change risks to better inform about the future investments and promote alternative solutions to tourism services.

Coastal and Maritime Tourism – Whale Watching case study

The Coastal and Maritime Tourism sector in Blue economy context it's a sector with an open scope inside the economy system. In this context, the Project develop the whale watching case study to experience the application of the developed framework in a more constrain scope of analysis and geographical scale.

There is a diversity of coastal and maritime recreation activities, in particular activities related to nature experiences that include land and sea wildlife watching. To explore the implications of climate change and climate change policies for island tourism, in SOCLIMPACT we focus on the case of whale-watching, a nautical tourism activity. Whale watching is a relevant activity in islands generating economic and other social, educational, scientific and recreational benefits for local communities. The whale watching activity has been suggested to play a leading role in the development of sustainable island-based tourism (Hoyt, 2005). The whale watching case study in

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SOCLIMPACT will allow for a detailed examination of climate impacts and adaptation at a national/regional scale. It will also allow for the exploration of sustainable tourism practices and their relevance in the context of climate change. In addition, the case study will bring practical and concrete knowledge to the extensive and complex coastal and maritime tourism sector. Therefore, the case study will be useful for generating and testing methodologies within WP7 framework in SOCLIMPACT.

Whale watching can be defined as commercial tours during which tourists can encounter cetaceans (whale, dolphin or porpoise species) in their natural habitat. Tours can take place by *boat, air or from land, to see, swim with, and/or listen* to cetacean species (Hoyt, 2001). Since the 80s the industry has grown worldwide and estimates (2008) indicate that nearly 13 million people went whale watching in 119 countries and overseas territories, spending more than USD \$2.1 billion (Hoyt, 2001; O'Connor *et al.*, 2009). In the Atlantic islands estimates indicate that approximately 1.7 million people per year go for whale watching activities, with a total expenditure of US\$133 million (Hoyt, 2005).

The impact of climate change on whale watching is largely unknown (Moreno, 2010). To date two frameworks have been developed to address climate change implications for the whale-watching industry. The first theoretical framework was developed by (Lambert *et al.*, 2010) and aims to evaluate the resilience of whale watching to climate change. Resilience was defined in this framework as the “degree of change in cetacean occurrence experienced before tourist numbers fall below a critical threshold.” The framework considers three variables: a) likelihood of observing a cetacean; b) trip type and c) tourist type. The quantification of the three variables indicates the level of resilience of the whale watching activity to changes in cetacean occurrence driven by climate change. Later, a second framework (Meynecke, Richards and Sahin, 2017) was developed through a stakeholders’ participatory approach on the east coast of Australia. This framework identified four key modules: 1) the biological module, focusing on the factors related to cetacean species; 2) the climate module which considers relevant climate variables; 3) the management module related to both species and the whale watching activity and; 4) the socio-economic module related, for example, to number and type of tourists, profit and costs of the activity.

However, knowledge on the quantification of effects in each component identified in both theoretical frameworks is to a large extent unknown. In addition, the effects between different components and how they interact to affect the tourism activity still need further research. Therefore, the practical application of a theoretical framework, quantifying the effects, in the SOCLIMPACT islands is a valuable contribution to address these knowledge gaps.

The whale-watching case study aims to identify, together with stakeholders, adaptation options for companies to be able to address the impacts of climate change.

Considering the broader mitigation and sustainability issues, some whale-watching companies are committed to reduce emissions and promote sustainable business practices. Some of the measures include recycling and minimizing waste, tracking the companies’ carbon footprint and measure of travel emissions and the acquisition of vessels able to maintain optimum fuel efficiency.

Various companies offer carbon-neutral tours and purchase carbon offsets, supporting the work of nonprofit conservation organizations.

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In addition, whale species are known to contribute to the oceans ability to absorb CO₂ and store organic carbon in the ocean. Whales consume prey at depth and defecate iron-rich liquid faeces into the photic zone, where it stimulates primary production and carbon export to the deep ocean (Lavery et al., 2010). In addition, whales' movements also enhance primary productivity by transporting nutrient rich water into the euphotic zone (Lavery et al., 2012).

Relevant policies concerning climate change and the whale-watching activity are related to: 1) maritime spatial planning and marine protected areas; 2) whale watching regulations (e.g. conduct code); 3) climate adaptation plans; 4) strategic and management plans for tourism.

3.3.2.4 Aquaculture

Aquaculture is the fastest growing food-producing sector (FAO, 2014). Regarding climate change policy, the implications of the Paris Climate Agreement for the sector are still to be assessed.

The potential impacts of climate change are related with seawater temperature, change in currents, and increased frequency and intensity of extreme weather events (FAO, 2014). In this context the regions included in the SOCLIMPACT Project should take measures to avoid potential decline of the aquaculture production over time, due to shifts in critical parameters related to climate. Short-term impacts on aquaculture will potentially be a substantial decrease in production and the destruction of the open-sea equipment and in-land infrastructures, due to extreme weather events. Changes in oceanic and atmospheric variables could also increase risks of diseases, parasites or harmful algae (FAO, 2014).

The focus of the international policy related to aquaculture is on food security production, especially for economies that are highly dependent on aquaculture production. Governance gaps and comprehensive policies in the sector are being framed internationally (FAO, 2014, 2017). However, in the context of climate change adaptation policies should be developed at regional and national levels as well (Techera, 2018)

Adaptation to climate change will need to increase the connection and competition between aquaculture, fisheries and agriculture products in perspective of the predicted impacts and to create solutions and response on food security production.

Relevant documents for the sector:

- *«Impacts of climate change on fisheries and aquaculture - Synthesis of current knowledge, adaptation and mitigation options»* Barange, M., Bahri, T., Beveridge, M.C.M., Cochrane, K.L., Funge-Smith, S. & Poulain, 2018 ;
- *«Adaptation strategies of the aquaculture sector to the impacts of climate change»* FAO, 2017
- *«The State of World Fisheries and Aquaculture»* FAO, 2014

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3.3.2.5 Maritime Transport

Marine transport will suffer climatic pressures associated with climate change from **sea level** (rise), different **sea conditions**, reduction of **days below freezing** and **reduction of sea ice** (European Commission, 2013a). The **Global Mean Sea Level (GMSL)** is a value parameter associated with climate change hazards at a global level, which may not be directly correspond to regional and local levels. “Most coastal regions in Europe have experienced an increase in absolute sea level and in sea level relative to land, but there is significant regional variation.” (Füssel *et al.*, 2017b). So “(...) planners (...)” will “(...) greatly benefit from more locally and regionally relevant information that accounts for location-specific adjustments to GMSL”. (Sweet *et al.*, 2017). This will have an effect on ships getting in and out of ports, as well as increased damage to harbors and pier defenses.

With the **regional sea level rise** to consider, there is the risk having navigability affected by changes in sedimentation rates and location of shoals with more frequent closure. The average **regional sea level** is an important parameter (on which others depend) for port planning and design, used for lay-outing facilities, breakwaters, making navigation assessments and wave penetration studies. If only this parameter changes in the future, there may be several relevant implications for ports and their operations.

Marine ports

Marine ports themselves will suffer from increased frequency of **extreme storm events (cyclones and storms, and waves height)**, (again) **sea level rise, ocean floods** and floods with **mass movements** (landslides). All these climatic hazards may create damage in infrastructure as well as interruptions and bottlenecks in the flow of products through ports (adapted from European Commission, 2013a).

This type of infrastructures has to be planned carefully based on prudent climate assumptions, as they have a long-life span, are heavy, tend to be one-off expensive investments (but may require maintenance or upgrades), have a strong impact in coastal zone management and are critical for society and the economy, especially in the context of islands. Climate change hazards add **uncertainty**, although manageable, in the decision making and design phase of **marine ports**, as projections on GMSL, extreme storm events and wave patterns carry in themselves uncertainty (Sweet *et al.*, 2017).

Relevant documents for the sector

As in the Energy sector, the **adaptation** framework set by the European Commission for the transport infrastructure also lays within the “Adapting Infrastructure to Climate Change” (European Commission, 2013a). It is recognized that “**Sea level rise** will exacerbate coastal inundation and magnify the effect of storm surges, thus threatening vital infrastructure, settlements and facilities that support the livelihoods of local communities”. “Due to the long-life span of the majority of transport infrastructure and their great economic value, their preparedness and resilience to future impacts of climate change are critical”. It recommends that “Adapting infrastructure to a changing climate needs to be considered in two ways. First, when constructing new infrastructure, climate resilience can be ensured by locating, designing and operating an asset

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with the **current and future climate in mind.**” “Secondly, existing infrastructure can be made more climate-resilient by **retrofitting** and/or ensuring that **maintenance** regimes incorporate resilience to the impacts of climate change over an asset’s lifetime.” This European framework provides a good starting point for the SOCLIMPACT framework regarding the marine transport sector.

For supplementary information about marine transport see Annex.

4 SOCLIMPACT Islands context

To characterize the Island under study it was relevant to define the limits of the methods used, the resolution the policy context for each island, and the level of development of the adaptation policy. For this aim the Island were characterizer in four key topics:

- 1) Significant climate events which occurred in the last 10 years with impacts on blue economy sectors.
- 2) General commitment with respect to regional application of national and international climate change and DRR policy (e.g.: objectives, goals, etc.).
- 3) Specific limits and obstacles faced in the region (e.g. resource limitations, lack of commitment, etc.).
- 4) Relevant documents for: climate change adaptation, climate change mitigation and disaster risk reduction in the region (e.g. Regional adaptation strategy, disaster risk plans, etc.).

The Island characterization are presented in the next chapters:

4.1 Azores

4.1.1 Significant climate events

The Azores islands have an autonomous adaptive capacity that was driven by centuries old exposure to harsh conditions presented by the North Atlantic sea. All aspects of life and infrastructure are designed to withstand stresses that a not applicable to mainland. For instance, storm Hercules brought high winds with gusts reaching 213 km/h occurred on the Flores island, in February 2014, during the night of 4 to 5, resulted in some damages to the energy grid. The same event would most likely cause havoc in Portuguese mainland, as it was the case of storm Leslie, where wind gusts of 176 km/h were recorded but where 200 high and medium voltage transmission towers were downed. Therefore, not neglecting existing vulnerabilities, the same events may have less impact in the Azores Islands than expected, especially when comparing with Portuguese main land infrastructure. Also there are significant differences regarding systems resilience inside the region and in different Island, for example, the occidental island can resist to extreme wind that would be problematic in the central islands.

Given this scenario a few examples where found that may have reached or surpass thresholds specific to the island's context, namely:

- Floods:
 - December 15th, 2009, Agualva (Terceira);
 - October 3rd, 2018, São Miguel;
 - November 25th, 2018, Angra do Heroísmo and Praia da Vitória (Terceira);
 - February 24th, 2019, Faial, Pico, São Jorge, Graciosa e Terceira;
- Storms:

- Nadine - September 20th, 2012, south of the Azores;
- Alex (Hurricane (F1)), São Miguel and Flores;
- Kyllian, February 22th, 2018, Terceira, São Miguel and Santa Maria;
- Landslide:
 - December 5th, 2010, Fajãzinha (Flores);
 - March 13th, 2013, Terceira and São Miguel;
 - October 29th, 2012, Flores.

4.1.2 General Commitment

Autonomous Region of the Azores has been working on defining a policy that allows it to face the major challenges and opportunities of climate change.

The Azores approved its Regional Strategy on Climate Change (ERAC) in 2011 (Resolution 123/2011). The ERAC is to be put into action through the Regional Program for Climate Change (PRAC) approved by Resolution of the Council of the Government 93/2014. The PRAC is focused in mitigation and adaptation to climate change to major economic sectors and natural assets, and its interaction with the climate.

PRAC program was conclude in 2016 and approved in October 2019 by the Azores Regional Assembly . In PRAC was developed SRIERPA (Sistema Regional de Inventário de Emissões por Fontes de Remoção por Sumidouros de Poluentes Atmosférico), a regional system of inventory and monitoring of carbon sinks and emissions, that feeds the IRERPA, with is the inventory itself monitoring of carbon sinks and emissions (Inventário de Emissões por Fontes de Remoção por Sumidouros de Poluentes Atmosféricos), was created within the scope of PRAC and seems to be still active (Despacho n.º 84/2018). This inventory produces results that comply with IPCC methods and that can be fully integrated with the national inventory system INERPA (Inventário Nacional de Emissões Atmosféricas), using the CRF (Common Reporting Format) and producing the NIR (National Inventory Report). This information is used by the UNFCCC (United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change) to assess the current status and evolution of compliance of nations with international commitments regarding emissions. The commitment with UNFCCC and national mitigation goals is stated in ERAC, PRAC and it is part of the standard official regional government speech.

The autonomous regional government continues to announce its commitment on renewable energy and future investments. Also, it must be noted that harsh consequences on fossil fuel-based energy have not been put in force, both in energy sector and the transport sector. Both sectors benefit from tax relieves given for the purchase of fuel-oil and diesel fuel that may come to end if the commitment to climate change reaches its full potential.

The expansion of renewable energy sources in the electric sector continued, for instance in 2017, the geothermal electricity plant started operation of 4 MW of stable production. The project started in the year 2000, first drills where made in 2007 and in 2015 the installation of a (predicted) 3.5

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MW went underway. This facility will provide for 10% of the electricity and intentions exist to increase the available power. There has been also the announcement of an energy plan with the 2030 horizon (Estratégia Açoriana para a Energia 2030) and a plan for the electrification of mobility (Estratégia para a Implementação da Mobilidade Elétrica nos Açores) which aims for having 2000 electric vehicles in the islands by 2030 as well. Both for the adaptation and mitigation part the PRAC contain recommendations regarding electric mobility that may shape its' future course.

To sum-up the regions commitment to fight climate change and deal with risks is:

Risk Assessment:

- (1) Improve the research capacity:
 - a. Climate;
 - b. Monitorization
 - c. Vulnerability assessment;

Mitigation:

- (1) Promote low carbon economy;
- (2) GEE emission sustainable reduction;
- (3) Integrate the mitigation objectives in the sectors;

Adaptation:

- (1) Build resilience for the territory;
- (2) Promote adaptative capacity on key sectors;
- (3) integrate the mitigation objectives in the sectors.

4.1.3 Specific limits and obstacle

The major constrain in this territory is the fact that this is an outermost Regions, some 1600 kms away from main land Portugal (locally referred as the continent). The dimension of some islands leads to a lack of critical mass to achieve economies of scale, making them economically depend from the outside. This reality is aggravated by the fact that this archipelago very spread out, stretching 600 kms from its further corners, grouped in three clusters, very much dependent on air and sea transport. The sea ports and airports tend to be oversized to ensure (whenever possible) regular direct connections to the main land (where feasible), even in through rough conditions, as those found in north Atlantic (frequent) storms.

Each island has an isolated electrical grid as the connection between different islands has not been possible to attain. A connection between Faial and Pico islands has been tried but failed due to technical and endurance difficulties. The advent of a sustainable energy grid linking some of the five islands of the central group could reshape their energy system, reducing context costs, increasing quality, reliability of service and ensuring the feasibility of further development of renewable energy.

4.1.4 Relevant documents

- ERAC (Climate Change Regional Strategy), 2013;

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- PRAC (Climate Change Regional Program), 2018;
- IRERPA, 2018;
- INERPA, 2018;

4.2 Balearic Islands

4.2.1 Significant climate events

Extreme flood event in the eastern part of Mallorca on October 2018 which caused 12 deaths and large economic losses. It was linked to weather extreme events but not with climate change (up to our knowledge).

Wild Fire in the northwestern part in July 2013, the largest recorded in Mallorca. It was caused by human error, but it is not clear yet the role of weather conditions on the intensity of it (dryness of the forest, temperatures)

Further information (in Spanish):

- “Siete días de la riada: Las inundaciones de Sant Llorenç en imágenes”, 15/10/2018
<https://www.diariodemallorca.es/mallorca/2018/10/15/inundaciones-sant-llorenç-imagenes/1356245.html>
- “Andratx: se cumplen tres meses del peor incendio forestal en Balears”, 28/10/2013
<https://www.ultimahora.es/sucesos/ultimas/2013/10/28/111272/andratx-cumplen-tres-meses-del-peor-incendio-forestal-balears.html>

4.2.2 General Commitment

The region should follow the commitments at European and Spanish level with a limited capacity of action as the responsibilities on energy or coastal infrastructures, for instance, are not all held at regional level.

In the case of the Balearic Region, and while the Spanish government is finalizing yet his Law on Climate Change, the Governing Council approved in February 2019, the Climate Change and Transition Law Energy of the Balearic Islands. This law is in line with the global targets of reduction of the EU by 2030 and 2050 and therefore obliges the Balearic Islands to be responsible in the reduction of emissions and the penetration of the renewable energies.

In the particular case of the Menorca island, there are several initiatives even more ambitious and the islands is being considered as a pilot case at EU level for the transition to decarbonized islands.

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4.2.3 Specific limits and obstacle

The present regional government is committed with the actions on climate change and adaptation, but there will be elections in a couple of months and is unknown what will be the position of the new government. This is a major concern as far as involvement on actions on climate change strongly depends on the color of the party.

Also, some strategies can be designed at regional level, but their effective implementation will depend on the regulations and strategies at National Level. Furthermore, actions at local level can face the opposition of some economic sectors (basically linked to tourism activities) which are strong and usually reluctant to changes.

4.2.4 Relevant documents

- Regional department on climate change:
<http://www.caib.es/govern/organigrama/area.do?coduo=2679877&lang=es>
- Regional roadmap for adaptation to climate change:
<http://www.caib.es/govern/sac/fitxa.do?codi=3098540&coduo=2679877&lang=es>
- Summary of the Regional Law on Climate Change and Energy Transition:
<http://www.caib.es/pidip2front/jsp/es/ficha-convocatoria/9199460>
- Assessment of vulnerability of the Balearic Islands:
<http://www.caib.es/govern/sac/fitxa.do?codi=3098540&coduo=2390767&lang=es>

4.3 Canary Islands

4.3.1 Significant climate events

One of the most relevant weather events has that has affected the Canary Islands in recent years has been the tropical storm “Delta”. It affected specially the islands of El Hierro, La Palma, Tenerife and Gran Canaria (the top part of a 30m high rock broke off and fell into the sea), although the most damaged island was Tenerife. The highest wind speed recorded was 200-248km/h. The storm and lasted two days (28th-28th November 2005).

Other relevant events are related to precipitations and floods; and strong winds: November-December 2009, February 2010, March 2013 (wind speed of 100-156km/h; and precipitations of 100-138 l/m²), October 2014 and October 2015.

Detailed information (in Spanish): <http://meteolamatanza.es/efemerides-meteorologicas-en-canarias/>

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4.3.2 General Commitment

According to this document, presented at the UN Climate Change Conference 2017, even if Canary Islands tried to pass an adaptation plan (reference 1) which includes advice for adaptation and mitigation policies, there is no policy implemented in Canary Islands in this respect.

There exists a document called “Canary Islands Strategy to Fight Against Climate Change “Estrategia canaria de lucha contra el cambio climático”, applicable to the Canary Islands (reference 5b), which was elaborated by the “Canary Agency for Sustainable Development and Climate Change” [“Agencia Canaria de Desarrollo Sostenible y Cambio Climático”]. This agency was active between 2009 and 2012, when it was extinguished by decree. Since then, it doesn't exist there is no organism institution in the Canary Government focused on addressing climate change issues; and the mentioned strategy strategic plan hasn't been reactivated nor updated.

Now, there exists a Committee of Experts advising the Regional Government (belonging to the executive power) which has at its disposal technical sub-committees in charge of this specific issues., but the information related to its activity should be provided by the Regional Government.

Between 2015 and 2018, the Executive Regional Government power has announced the setting up of the Canary Islands Observatory of Climate Change (Observatorio Canario de Cambio Climático), an organism which creation was proposed in 2015 by the Cabildo [Island Authority hall] de of Lanzarote. However, the regulation of this organism institution hasn't been provided yet, and there's does not dispose of structural staff specific personnel yet. Also, in 2018 it was announced the formation creation of a Climate Change Commission, associated advising to the Presidency of the Canary Government, and also the presentation of a draft bill for Climate Change in Canary Islands, but these initiatives haven't been materialized yet.

In conclusion, the Canary Islands have not updated strategy strategic plan that considers adaptation and mitigation policies for the islands, being this a priority objective for the canary Canary Islands society, its territory and its productive sectors.

The islands of La Gomera, Gran Canaria and Lanzarote have at their disposal recent Strategies and Actions Action Plans regarding Climate Change, thanks to their Island Authorities hall (Cabildo). However, only the island of Gran Canaria has activated the passing and implementation in the Governing Council of its Action Plan, whose horizons and objectives are set for 2030-2050. In addition, Gran Canaria has developed and executed in the last three years numerous initiatives related to global warming. It has promoted several projects with the Spanish Government (OECC – Oficina Española de Cambio Climático), the Fundación Biodiversidad, the convention of United Nations for Climate Chante (UNFCC), the European Commission (Joint Research Centre), and numerous collectives and social agents of the island.

The Cabildo Island Authority of Gran Canaria has promoted with support of The Canary Islands Institute of Technology, in parallel, in the last two years (2017, 2018), the adherence of the island's municipalities to the EC initiative of The Covenant of Mayors, and development developed of the StrategyStrategic Energy and Climate Action Plans (SECAPs). Plans for Climate and Sustainable Energy [Planes de Acción por el Clima y la Energía Sostenible (PACES10 of all the 21 municipalities of the island have their own action plansSECAPs and their inventory of greenhouse gas emission inventory to work on its the progressive reduction of CO2 emission in the coming

years. The other 11 municipalities are in the process of elaborating their SECAPs. Finally, the Cabildo Island Authority of Gran Canaria has worked since 2017 together with the Agencia Estatal de Meteorología (AEMET) to sign a specific agreement about Adverse Meteorological Events [Fenómenos Meteorológicos Adversos (FMA)] in Gran Canaria. On the other hand, in the framework of the INTERREG MAC programme a project was submitted was elaborated and presented by the Cabildo Island Authority of Gran Canaria in 2018 to work in the Macaronesian area on Climate Change (other participants: AEMET, OECC, Governments of Senegal, Mauritania and Cabo Verde, ULPGC, Cabildos de El Hierro, Lanzarote and Tenerife).

4.3.3 Specific limits and obstacle

There is the need for more multilevel governance, and stronger main limitation faced is the lack of commitment of the regional government regarding this issue. A group of experts (Grupo de Acción Climática de Gran Canaria) wrote a roadmap, which was not implemented afterwards (reference 1).

Moreover, the strategies are carried out at island level, meaning that in many cases there is no consensus or homogenization of the topic in the different islands. For instance, the Cabildo Island Authority of Gran Canaria cooperates with the Canary Islands Institute of Technology in the elaboration of the SECAPs for its municipalities, and collaborate with the national agency of meteorology (AEMET), while other islands are not addressing the problem ([here](#)).

According to an expert in this issue: “the most important and severe limitation is the lack of political willingness to design and address a strategic plan that allows to have:

- a) An updated strategy regarding the impacts in all productive sectors to promote adaptation policies.
- b) An updated strategy regarding emissions in all sectors to promote mitigation policies about Greenhouse Gas Emissions, with the aim of working on the EU and IPCC proposals (reduce emissions about 45% in 2030 based on 2010's registration, and by 100% in 2050).”

Other Canary Islands entities, such as the Canary Islands Institute of Technology (ITC), Universidad de La Laguna, Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, WWF, ITC, PLOCAN, Centro UNESCO Gran Canaria, Asociación Domitila, Ben Magec-Ecologistas en Acción, Muévete por el Clima, Fundación Orotava de la Ciencia, among others, promote the research and dissemination of climate change impacts, but better coordination is needed among them and are not coordinated with the Regional Government, the 7 Island Authorities and the 88 municipalities, which may not ensure the efficient implementation in the islands of all the plans addressing climate change.

4.3.4 Relevant documents

- [Climate Change Adaptation Plan for Canary Islands \(2011\)](#)
- [Provide public information regarding the adaptation plan](#)
- [Climate Change Adaptation Plan](#) (2014-2018), follow-up (National level)
- [AdapteCCa](#)

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- [Measures against Climate Change](#)
- Applicable [regulation](#) at National level
- [Strategies for Canary Islands](#) to fight against climate change (includes a mitigation plan)

4.4 Corsica

4.4.1 Significant climate events

- Heatwave (2017)
- Drought (2018) and regular forest fires in summer
- Rainfall (22/10/2008 and 23/10/2008, 8/02/2017 and 09/02/2017)
- Floods in March 2013

More information:

<http://pluiesextremes.meteo.fr/france-metropole/Corse-13695.html>

<http://pluiesextremes.meteo.fr/france-metropole/-Evenements-memorables-.html>

<https://www.unige.ch/environnement/fr/home/actualites-2016/projet-anywhere>

4.4.2 General Commitment

Island scale:

- Climate Change Adaptation Plan - Corsica Basin
- The Plan for Development and Sustainable Development of Corsica (PADDUC)
- The Regional Plan of Climate of Air and Energy (SRCAE)
- Multiannual Energy Program (PPE)
- MedCOP (<https://www.medcop-programme.org>)
- Territorial Climate-Air-Energy Plans (PCAET)
- The Regional Plan for Air Quality: <https://www.ca-ajaccien.corsica/climat-air-energie-bruit/>
- National Strategy for Integrated Coastline Management: <http://www.geolittoral.developpement-durable.gouv.fr/strategie-nationale-de-gestion-integree-du-trait-r434.html>

National scale:

- Climate-Impact Knowledge GICC 1999
- National Strategy 2007
- National consultation
- PNACC (National Plan for Adaptation to Climate Change) 2011-2015
- 2015 PNACC Assessment
- Proposal Development 2016-2017
- 2019 PNACC (second)

4.4.3 Specific limits and obstacle

- Key land use, spatial planning, urban planning and maritime spatial planning policies do not consider the impacts of climate change
- Initiatives disconnected from the metropolitan territory sometimes

4.4.4 Relevant documents

- <http://www.corse.developpement-durable.gouv.fr/les-plans-climat-air-energie-territoriaux-pcaet-a353.html>
- https://www.corse.fr/Le-Schema-Regional-du-Climat-de-l%E2%80%8C-Air-et-de-l%E2%80%8C-Energie_a3945.html
- <https://www.corse.fr/attachment/474382/>
- https://www.corse.fr/Le-Plan-Regional-pour-la-Qualite-de-l-Air_a2640.html
- https://www.iucn.org/sites/dev/files/changement_climatique_et_milieu_marin_en_corse.pdf
- https://www.eaurmc.fr/jcms/pro_94072/fr/plan-d-adaptation-au-changement-climatique-bassin-de-corse
- <https://www.ca-ajaccien.corsica/wp-content/uploads/2018/01/PCET.pdf>
- <http://www.haute-corse.gouv.fr/plans-de-prevention-du-risque-inondation-r144.html>
- <http://www.corse-du-sud.gouv.fr/le-risque-inondation-a1983.html>
- <http://www.haute-corse.gouv.fr/plans-de-prevention-du-risque-incendie-de-foret-r327.html>
- https://www.ecologique-solidaire.gouv.fr/sites/default/files/2018.12.20_PNACC2.pdf

- <http://www.oehc.corsica/Actualites/Plan-d-adaptation-au-changement-climatique>
- <http://interreg-maritime.eu/fr/web/maregot/projet>
- <http://www.littoral-corse.fr/ADAPTO>
- <https://circle-2.wixsite.com/adapt-med>

4.5 Crete

4.5.1 Significant climate events

- **Wildfire** 29/5/2013 regional unit of Chania estimated disaster COST 1.915.545€
- **Floods** 12-13/2/2019 & 24-25/2/2019 regional unit of Chania (4 deaths and one person missing) first estimation of disaster cost 100.000.000 €

4.5.2 General Commitment

- The Region of Crete is in the process of submitting a proposal for the Regional Adaptation Strategy for Climate Change.
- The Regional Plan for Adaptation to Climate Change will be funded in accordance with the legislation in force.
- The objective of the Region of Crete is to draw up a plan that will provide answers around the actions that will have to be implemented against climate change, which affects everyday life, local economy, agriculture, livestock farming, fisheries, tourism and more.
- Adaptation to Climate change may include prevention and management of climate risks, for example erosion, fires, floods, storms and drought, including awareness raising, policy protection and systems and infrastructures disaster management.

4.5.3 Specific limits and obstacle

- Until nowadays, spatial planning, urban planning and maritime spatial planning policies do not consider the impacts of climate change.
- Regional Policies depend on National Policies and National Legislation to be followed. The main obstacles are slow procedures due to bureaucracy and funding constraints.

4.5.3.1 Relevant documents

- [National Strategy for Climate Change](#)

- The no. 11258 / 6-3-2017 (Government Gazette 873 / B' / 16-3-2017) on "Specialization of Regional Content Climate Change Adaptation Plans in accordance with Article 43 of Law 4414/2016 (A149): [link](#)

4.6 Cyprus

4.6.1 Significant climate events

Major events

- Severe drought in 2008, with water imported from Greece to satisfy drinking water demand and imposed restrictions on water supply for both households and agriculture.
- Drought and forest fire in 2016.

More common events

- Frequent dust storms in 2018 from the Saharan desert have caused an increase in respiratory problems for certain groups of the population.

Frequent heatwaves have caused increased need for power generation and subsequent cost for cooling in the summer months.

4.6.2 General Commitment

Climate Change action at European and National level

- 1992 Adoption of the United Nations Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) to stabilize concentrations of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere at levels that prevent dangerous impacts on the climate from human activities.
- 1994 UNFCCC entered into force
- 1997 Cyprus ratified the UNFCCC as a non-Annex I Party
- 1998 Adoption of the Kyoto Protocol to limit greenhouse gas emissions for the periods 2008-2012 and 2013-2020
- 2003 Cyprus ratified the Kyoto Protocol
- 2008 Start of the Kyoto Protocol's First Commitment period
- 2009 EU's Climate and Energy Package for 2020 agreed
- 2011 Cyprus changed its UNFCCC status to Annex I party
- 2011 EU's 2050 Roadmap agreed
- 2012 End of the Kyoto Protocol's First Commitment period
- 2012 Doha amendment to the Kyoto Protocol for 2013-2020
- 2015 Adoption of the Paris Agreement to reduce greenhouse gas emissions.

- 2016 Paris Agreement entered into force
- 2017 Cyprus ratified the Paris Agreement

Policies

- The River Basin Management Plan and Water Policy, drafted in the framework of the Water Framework Directive
- The Flood Risk Management Plan, drafted in the of the Floods Directive
- The National energy efficiency action plan of Cyprus, drafted in the framework of the Energy Efficiency Directive
- The National Renewable Energy Action Plan drafted in the framework of the 2009/28/EC Directive
- The Nearly Zero Energy Buildings Action Plan drafted in the framework of the Energy Performance of Building Directive
- The European Common Agriculture Policy
- The National Biodiversity Strategy. Cyprus has formulated the National Biodiversity Strategy (NBS) during 2013, as a reference document in order to fulfil the commitments accepted with the ratification of the Convention on Biological Diversity.
- The Strategy for the Management of waste
- The low-carbon development strategy of Cyprus to 2050
- The Multiannual national plan for the development of sustainable aquaculture

Climate Change mitigation and adaptation

- Reduction in greenhouse gas emissions and adaptation to climate change.
- Implementation of international and EU commitments on climate change, protection of the ozone layer and regulation and monitoring of fluorinated greenhouse gases.
- Coordination of climate change policy issues

Environmental protection

- Protection of the environment from the activities of industrial and livestock installations, waste management operators and waste producers.
- Managing species and habitats with the objective of halting the degradation of the conservation status.

- Assessment of the impacts on the environment from plans / programmes / projects and other actions

Efficient protection of forests against fires and other agents

- Protection of forests against forest fires.
- Protection of forests against other agents.

Protection of biodiversity and other ecosystem services

- Protection of biodiversity and other ecosystem services.
- Adaptation of forests to climate change and contribution of forests to mitigating climate change.

Safeguard the quality and protect the water resources and aquatic environment

- Implementation of the Floods Directive 2007/60/EC.

Protection and conservation of the marine environment

- Studies and monitoring of the marine waters up to the EEZ, under the relevant European legislation and International Conventions.
- Management and Monitoring of Marine Protected Areas.
- Inspection and combat of oil pollution (combat teams).
-

4.6.3 Specific limits and obstacle

A dedicated process is in place to facilitate stakeholders' involvement in the preparation of adaptation policies. However, there is little (mainly sectoral) evidence of transboundary cooperation to address common challenges with relevant neighboring countries (cooperation between Mediterranean countries).

There are a few organizations that are responsible for observing the impacts of climate change in various sectors (and monitoring of environmental variables).

Climate risks/vulnerability assessments do not take transboundary risks into account, when relevant. It is unclear how Cyprus will address climate risks transcending the country's frontiers (e.g., risks coming from warmer countries, changes in the Mediterranean, etc.)

It is unclear how knowledge gaps are used to prioritize funding in the field of adaptation research. Some research into the assessment of existing and future impacts on vulnerable economic sectors

is being financed and carried out through one-off projects. It has been decided to assess all knowledge gaps related to climate change impacts and adaptation and identify possible sources of funding for their research.

Education materials or specific training activities to build adaptation capacity or to help stakeholders to adapt to climate change are not yet available.

There are no updated sources of information available on climate change data and adaptation policy developments. Cyprus developed a CYPADAPT portal to support the dissemination of information on climate change adaptation. The platform was expected to provide access and share information and views on many different issues concerning adaptation options, climate impacts, vulnerability, case studies, research activities, legislation, financing opportunities, tools for adaptation planning and useful links, but has not been updated since 2014.

Very few mechanisms are in place to coordinate disaster risk management and climate change adaptation. Disaster risk reduction plans do not factor in projected climate extremes that may occur in the future, while the national adaptation strategy does not mention specific disaster preparedness plans or how these account for climate change adaptation.

Funding is available to increase climate resilience in vulnerable sectors and for cross-cutting adaptation action, but other elements, such as coordination, governance, capacity building, indicators and projections do not have specific allocation of resources. Also, costs of climate change impacts and costs/benefits of adaptation in general have yet to be identified.

The Cypriot authorities just started harmonizing national legislation and mainstream adaptation to reflect the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) Directive.

Key land use, spatial planning, urban planning and maritime spatial planning policies do not consider the impacts of climate change.

4.6.4 Relevant documents

- Department of Environment (2016). [Εθνική Στρατηγική για την Προσαρμογή στην Κλιματική Αλλαγή](#) (National Strategy for the Adaptation to Climate Change). Nicosia: Ministry of Agriculture, Rural Development and Environment.
- Department of Environment (2015). [Strategic Plan for Environment and Natural Resources](#). Nicosia: Ministry of Agriculture, Rural Development and Environment.
- Department of Environment (2016). [The Cyprus Climate Change Risk Assessment Evidence Report](#). Nicosia: Ministry of Agriculture, Rural Development and Environment.
- Zachariadis, T. (2016). [Climate Change in Cyprus: Review of the Impacts and Outline of an Adaptation Strategy](#). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Audit Office (2012). [Adapting to Climate Change – Facing Today the Challenges of the Future](#). Nicosia: Audit Office.

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- Department of Environment (2018). [Seventh National Communication & Third Biennial Report - under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change](#). Nicosia: Ministry of Agriculture, Rural Development and Environment.

4.7 Fehmarn

4.7.1 Significant climate events

The summer of 2018 was exceptional hot and dry in Germany and also in Fehmarn. Due to the heat there was a severe shortage of freshwater in the summer, although the islands water supply is largely provided by a connection to the main land.

Additionally, there were many fires that broke out on agricultural areas. This put the mostly voluntary firefighters up to their limits

A huge bloom of Cyanobacteria broke out in parts of the Baltic sea, due to warm water temperatures and eutrophication and severely harmed tourism especially on polish beaches in early summer. Thanks to tides and wind direction the Cyano did not hit Fehmarn, but they are a constant threat for tourism under climate change conditions.

Also, fire jellyfish are a danger for tourism, there were some incidents and some days in the season, where swimming in the sea had to be prohibited. Although there is a correlation between the amount of fire jellyfish and warm temperatures it is not linear. Here other factors such as tides and overfishing (loss of natural enemies) have to be considered.

4.7.2 General Commitment

Climate politics are applied on different political levels that have to be differentiated. Mitigation concepts do exist on all these levels (national, federal state of Schleswig-Holstein, Region of Ostholstein, City of Fehmarn).

The picture looks different for adaptation policy. While there is a strategy for Climate Adaptation on national Level () and federal state Level such strategies for the Region or the island are still missing, except for coastal protection and dyke building plans that always existed for coastal regions. On Fehmarn island level our stakeholders are open to develop strategic answers to climate change with SOCLIMPACT as a starting point

4.7.3 Specific limits and obstacle

The commitment for climate adaptation in the region is limited, since most municipalities have not yet discussed adaptation measures apart from the traditional coast protection and dyke building plans. But slowly things start to change, as not only the past summer has shown the need for action, but also because the national government finances scientific research and projects that develop good practice implementation principles.

Nevertheless, personal capacities for climate adaptation in the administrations of regions/municipalities are still not existent (or if yes only on the basis of project funding) and

budgets are not coherent as they are distributed over several already existing positions such as firefighting, building, health, port administration, beach management.

4.7.4 Relevant documents

Mitigation

- [Climate Mitigation in the Region Ostholstein](#)

Adaptation

- [German Adaptation Strategy \(DAS\)](#)
- [Adaptation Strategy of the Federal State of Schleswig-Holstein](#)
- [Project Radost - Climate Adaptation at German Baltic Coasts](#)
- Project Radost Website: <https://klimzug-radost.de/>

4.8 Madeira

4.8.1 Significant climate events

Flash flood in Funchal on the 20th February 2010: On 20 of February 2010 a heavy rain in the high peaks of Madeira caused a massive flash flood in Funchal and Ribeira Brava causing 47 victims, 250 wounded, 600 displaced persons, and 217 million € in damages, affecting the commerce, the services (electric grid, water supply), infrastructures (road and ports) and the tourism activity.

Link with photos: <https://funchalnoticias.net/2017/02/21/20-de-fevereiro-alguns-ja-se-esqueceram-que-aconteceu-fotos/>

Destructive waves 10th December 2013: During the days 10 and 11 of December of 2013 giant waves crushed against the harbours located on the southeast side of Madeira. In Machico the waves passed over the harbour causing structural damages in the infrastructure and sinking around 30 boats. One person lost his live trying to protect his boat. Also during this event heavy rains caused landslides disrupting the normal circulation of vehicles.

Links with videos: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hH--owHb2uM&feature=youtu.be>; <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MT5hieMMPT4>; <https://sicnoticias.pt/pais/2013-12-16-Prejuizos-do-mau-tempo-na-Madeira>

Windstorms 2018: 3rd of March of 2018, 24th of April of 2018, 8th of August of 2018, 4th of October of 2018, 13th of October of 2018, 28th of October of 2018, 5th of November of 2018 and 26th of November of 2018, etc. During these days the Airport of Madeira was conditioned due strong winds in the east side of Madeira. In total, 4% of all flights between January and September of 2018 were affected by windstorms.

Flash flood in Porto da Cruz on the 28th and 29th of November of 2013: During these days a heavy rain on the north cost of Madeira caused massive landslides that destructed houses and roads in the town of Porto da Cruz.

Fires 18th July of 2012: This fire burned several houses and forest area and displacing about 100 persons.

Fires 8-9th August 2016: This fire started in the forest area and reach the Funchal city center causing 3 victims and 61 million of damages in the city infrastructures with more than 300 buildings affected, displacing about 1000 persons.

Sea storm 25th of February of 2018 and 17th of November of 2018: During these dates the ferry that connects Madeira to Porto Santo suspended his activities due the sea storms.

4.8.2 General Commitment

The Autonomous Region of Madeira is signatory of two commitments in the scope of Climate Change:

1 - Pact of Island sign by the Regional Government on April 2011 – Is a binding instrument through which the island's authorities commits to go beyond the objectives set by the EU for 2020, reducing the CO₂ emissions in their respective territories by at least 20%, contributing to the achievement of the sustainable goals of the European Union for the year 2020.

Website: <https://www.sustainableislands.eu/pact-of-islands/what-is-pact-of-islands.html>

2 - *Compromisso 2020* – Establishes the framework for the implementation of the structural funds during the 2014-2020 programming period.

The *Compromisso 2020* states that is important to develop an upstream work of reinforce the knowledge about future and current events related with climate change, integrating international networks of research and sharing the knowledge and the good practices of intervention.

In parallel, it is necessary to develop approaches of interaction among different regional authorities (health, tourism, hydric resources, forests, etc.) to identify intervention measures that assure:

- Dissemination of scientific knowledge and good practices of adaptation;
- Preventive measures of vulnerabilities and effects' mitigation;
- Elaboration of strategic and operational orientations for adaptation to climate change on global and sectorial aspects.

Link: [site compromissomadeira2020](#) (Page 66)

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4.8.3 Specific limits and obstacle

Limitation faced by Madeira are:

- The absence of equipment's to systematically collect representative climatic data for Madeira Island namely sea temperature, wave characteristics, currents;
- The small and isolated electricity grid limits the penetration of intermittent renewable energies;
- The financing limitations to invest in adaptation measures such as: water collection and storage solutions and reforestation.

UPDATE:

- Madeira already has an early warning systems of flash floods. It can predict them a flash flood six hours in advance. The system's name is Flash Flood Alert Systems (SAARAM)

Link: <https://www.rtp.pt/madeira/sociedade/sistema-de-alerta-de-aluvioes-continua-em-testes-15463>

Madeira is also developing the Regional Strategy Against Fires (PRDFCI) and will be fully developed until August of 2020.

4.8.4 Relevant documents

Sustainable Energy Action Plans (SEAP) in the scope of Pact of Islands – According with these plans the futures policies for energy will be oriented to ensure energy supply guarantee, economic and environmental sustainability of the sector and quality of energy services, and to contribute to job creation, regional added value and competitiveness of the regional economy.

SEAP for Madeira Island Link: aream.pt

SEAP for Porto Santo Island Link: aream.pt

Sustainable Energy Action Plans (SEAP) in the scope of Covenant of mayors for climate and energy: aream.pt

Climate change adaptation documents:

Strategy CLIMA-Madeira, strategy for adaptation to climate change of the Autonomous Region of Madeira.

This strategic document aims to:

- Enhance the knowledge about the relation between the climatic system and the natural and human systems;

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- Reduce the vulnerability for the impacts of climate change;
- Explore the opportunities created by climate change;
- Promote adaptation measures based on evidences from scientific studies and good practices;
- Integrate the adaptations measures in the current governmental instruments;
- Promote the involvement and the synergies among the interested parts in the process of adaptation.

Link: clima.madeira.pt

Plan for the risk of flood management of the Autonomous Region of Madeira (PGRI-RAM 2016-2021) – in the Link below it can be find the Google Drive folder with the documents regarding the studies of Flooding Risk.

Assessing the flood risk in Madeira Island – this article contains a set of measures and instruments, namely structural measures that aim the mitigation of the damages caused by the heavy rains.

Link: poseur.portugal2020.pt

hydrogeomorphological risks – In the page 77 it can be find the measures proposed to reinforce the adaptation capacity of Madeira island regarding the risk of floods

Link: clima.madeira.pt

4.9 Malta

4.9.1 Significant climate events

There were no recent significant climate events recorded in Malta in the last 10 years. The events that occurred during that time can be categorized as natural fluctuations of weather patterns.

However, it is worth to be mentioned, that October 2018 was the stormiest month since 1951 and that whole year the stormiest year ever ([see here](#)). Additionally, snowfall was recorded in December 2014 in Malta, which is rare but should not be considered as a significant climate change event ([see here](#)).

Signs of climate change can rather be found in the increase of the mean air temperature and decrease of precipitation. The period of 1981-2015 shows a warming trend of +0.22°C per decade. The sea surface temperature of the Mediterranean Sea increased at a rate of +0.35°C per decade, which has resulted in changes of species composition and species life cycles, as well as the increase of abundance of alien species. The total yearly precipitation showed a decrease at a rate of -6.3 mm per decade over the period 1981-2015, however, this trend was not found to be statistically significant ([see here](#)).

4.9.2 General Commitment

UNFCCC

- “Malta ratified the UNFCCC in 1994 and the Kyoto Protocol in 2001. These ratifications were made based on non-Annex I status. To this effect, Malta did not immediately take on any quantified emission limitation or reduction obligations under these international instruments; thus, it did not have a quantified target for the limitation or reduction of greenhouse gas emissions for the first Kyoto Protocol Commitment Period (CP1; 2008-2012).” ([see here](#)).
- (Decision 1/CP.16 The Cancun Agreements: Outcome of the work of the Ad Hoc Working Group on Long-term Cooperative Action under the Convention ([see here](#))).
- In 2010 Malta became an Annex I party to the UNFCCC which signified the intention of Malta to step up against climate change ([see here](#)).

EU Law

- Monitoring Mechanism (Regulation (EU) No 525/2013) - report an annual national GHG inventory (mechanism for monitoring and reporting greenhouse gas emissions and for reporting other information at national and Union level relevant to climate change and repealing Decision No 280/2004/EC ([see here](#))).
- EU Emission Trading Scheme (EU ET; Directive 2003/87/EC)

Effort-Sharing Decision (Decision 406/2009/EC): “Malta is committed to remain in line with the Effort Sharing Decision (Decision No406/2009/EC of 23 April 2009) thereby conforming to a reduction of its GHG emission growth by no more than 5% on 2005 levels by 2020.” ([see here](#))

4.9.3 Specific limits and obstacle

Since the implementation of the Climate Adaption Strategy, adaption action has not been a primary focus of Malta’s authorities. One reason for that can be the small size of the country which limits the range of issues that authorities can address ([see here](#)).

Additionally, Malta’s number of inhabitants and cars on the island is increasing which results in the need to widen existing roads and to build new ones. Little is done to curtail emissions from

transport, which is one of the main contributors of GHG. This seems to jar with Malta's commitment to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and will make it difficult for the country to meet its emission targets ([see here](#)).

The rapidly increasing number of inhabitants on the island also triggers the boom of construction, which converses more and more green areas into building sites which further limits the ability to absorb Carbon dioxide from the atmosphere.

There is an overall lack of subject-specific studies to estimate the impact and its costs of climate change and the required adaption([see here](#)).

4.9.4 Relevant documents

Malta's' National Strategy for Policy and Abatement Measures relating to the Reduction of Greenhouse Gas Emissions ([see here](#)).

- Published and adopted in 2009
- Includes 96 actions for the time period 2009-2020

National Climate Change Adaption Strategy ([see here](#))

- Adopted in 2012
- "recommending the necessary adaptation measures deemed relevant to sectors that are vulnerable to a changing climate through a set of 72 actions which addresses the following areas: agriculture, biodiversity, fresh water resources and coastal zones, land degradation, fisheries and migration. It also addresses issues related to financial impacts and sustainability."3
- Adaption action plans were not developed due to the small size of the state.

Climate Action Act ([see here](#))

- Adopted in 2015
- Framework for climate action Malta
- "This Act provides for action in order to contribute to the mitigation of climate change by limiting anthropogenic emissions of greenhouse gases and protecting and enhancing greenhouse gas sinks and reservoirs, and to contribute to the prevention, avoidance and reduction of the adverse impacts of climate change and the reduction of vulnerability, enhancement of resilience, and adaptation to the adverse effects of climate change."

Malta's Low Carbon Development Strategy ([see here](#))

- In development now (started in May 2017)
- Based on UN Framework Convention on Climate Change, Paris Agreement and Regulation (EU) N0 525/2013 of the European Parliament.

4.10 Sardinia

4.10.1 Significant climate events

10 - 11st of October 2018 – storm torrential rains and violent thunderstorms caused damage to the infrastructures, and stopped road, airport and maritime traffic.

23rd of October 2008 – flood - torrential rains and violent thunderstorms caused damage to the infrastructures, flooding in the cities and river flooding in the land and landslide.

4.10.2 General Commitment

According to the Regional Adaptation Strategy, the general commitments are:

- 1) Create a context of suitable conditions for adaptation, acting on the level of rules and process management;
- 2) Create and support the ability to adapt, through knowledge and skills and their circulation, also providing the potential tools for the implementation of adaptation;
- 3) Indicate effective paths of adaptation, integrating techniques, technologies and methodologies, giving priority to ecological, social and economic sustainability.

Furthermore, the general objectives contained in the Regional strategy are:

- 1) Minimize the risks arising from climate change;
- 2) Protect the health, well-being and assets of the population;
- 3) Preserving the natural heritage;
- 4) Maintain or improve the resilience and adaptability of natural, social and economic systems;
- 5) Take advantage of any opportunities that might arise with the new weather conditions.

4.10.3 Specific limits and obstacle

Until now days, spatial planning, urban planning and maritime spatial planning policies do not consider the impacts of climate change.

Regional Policies depend on National Policies and National Legislation to be followed. The main obstacles are slow procedures due to bureaucracy and funding constraints.

A limit is represented by the lower awareness of Local Authorities, the Sardinia Region aims to increase the awareness of the problem to stimulate a dialogue between all stakeholders and actors in order to facilitate the promotion and implementation of effective actions.

4.10.4 Relevant documents

- National Climate Change Adaptation Strategy (SNAC): [see here](#)
- Regional Climate Change Adaptation Strategy (SRACC): [see here](#)
- Strategic plan for aquaculture in Italy 2014-2020
- Regional strategic plan of tourism development 2018/2021 of the Sardinia region: [see here](#)
- Plan for the Hydrogeological Asset of the Sardinia Region: [see here](#)
- Map of Environmentally Sensitive Areas To Desertification, ESAS: [see here](#)
- Regional plan for programming the activities of prevision, prevention and active fight for the defense of vegetation against fire (year of revision 2018): [see here](#)
- Protection plan of waters – Sardinia region: [see here](#)
- [MasterAdapt](#) project: [see here](#)
- [Clisel](#) project
- [Maregot](#) project

4.11 Sicily

4.11.1 Significant climate events

- 24/02/2019, strong wind caused infrastructural damages
- 2-3 November 2018, torrential rains and violent thunderstorms caused damage to the infrastructures, flooding in the cities and river flooding in the land and landslide.
- 27 September 2018, Mediane.
- 04 August 2018, twister in Pantelleria.
- 26 June 2018, twister near Erice (Trapani).
- 28 November 2017, windstorm, caused damage to the infrastructures and stopped maritime traffic
- 10 October 2015, windstorms, torrential rains and violent thunderstorms caused damage to the infrastructures, flooding in the cities and river flooding in the land and landslide.
- 14 August 2013, twister near Enna.

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- 22 December 2009, windstorm, caused damage to the infrastructures and stopped airport and maritime traffic.

4.11.2 General Commitment

Proposal of an integrated national plan for energy and climate (31/12/2018): To support and provide a robust analytical basis for the National Integrated Energy and Climate Plan (PNEC), the following were implemented:

- a BASE scenario that describes an evolution of the energy system with current policies and measures;
- a PNEC scenario that quantifies the strategic objectives of the plan.

The PNEC tables illustrate the main objectives of the 2030 plan on renewables, energy efficiency and greenhouse gas emissions and the main measures envisaged to achieve the objectives of the Plan.

National Plan of Adaptation to Climate Change (July 2017): this plan identifies and discusses the main objectives to be pursued and the necessary steps, for each one of the socio-economic and environmental sectors of interest, based on the climatic and impact analyzes to face the impacts of the expected climate changes.

From the sector analysis, over 350 actions emerged that were collected in a single Database that contains detailed analytical information for each individual action and different selection keys for the actions to allow easy search and consultation of the same.

There are 13 cross-cutting actions that are common to all the sectors analyzed and which have a national value, together with more specific actions for each sector.

The actions identified for each sector are associated with the impacts identified in the previous analyzes, the adaptation targets to be pursued and the homogeneous climatic areas of implementation, suggested based on the RCP 4.5 climate scenario identified as the reference scenario.

4.11.3 Specific limits and obstacle

Different kind of limits and barriers, respectively experienced by individuals, organizations and local governments, exist.

From the point of view of individuals, a general low personal understanding of climate change and its impacts exists.

Considering organizations (both private and public) we can highlight different barriers:

- inadequate funds for adaptation, especially the financial ones
- uncertainty around the scale of the climate changes and the concrete risks

- lack of locally relevant and practical information about potential climate impacts
- limited financial resources both for medium sized organizations and local governments
- culture of the organization

Specifically, for local governments, there is a difficult in planning

4.11.4 Relevant documents

- Proposal of an integrated national plan for energy and climate (31/12/2018)
- National Plan of Adaptation to Climate Change (July 2017)
- Sicily has not launched specific initiatives for the preparation of Strategies and/or Plans but has ongoing activities preliminary to these paths. The process began with the drafting of the ERDF OP 2014-2020 - Objective 5 where climate adaptation is considered unifying and transversal for the reduction of exposure to natural risk.
- Strategic plan for aquaculture in Italy 2014-2020
- Regional Plan of Transport and Mobility (Sicily Region)
- Regional strategic plan of tourism development 2019/2023 -three-year program of tourism development 2019/2021 of the Sicilian region
- Plan for the Hydrogeological Asset of the Sicilian Region
- Map of vulnerable areas at desertification risk of in Sicily
- Regional plan for programming the activities of prevision, prevention and active fight for the defense of vegetation against the fire (year of revision 2018)

4.12 West Indies

4.12.1 Significant climate events

The Lesser Antilles experiences a hurricane season from June to November. Six long months of hurricane season that durably affect the tourist season and the Antilles economy. The historical database over the last 400 years demonstrate the recurrence of these events. The 2017 season was marked for example by 3 major events (Irma, Maria and José) of category 4 and 5, never seen before. The French part of the island of Saint-Marteen (Saint-Martin) was deeply impacted by the hurricane Irma at 95%. The economy of the island based mainly on tourism is struggling to recover. The southern part of Guadeloupe was severely impacted by the hurricane Maria, destroying all the banana's plantations. These cyclonic events and their induced consequences (storm surges), to which must be added the usual atmospheric disturbances (storms, intense rainfall, floods) are the main climatic hazards of the region that affect tourism significantly

4.12.2 General Commitment

The policy of adaptation to these endemic natural hazards is based first of all on national laws and a culture of a feedback experiences. More recently the public policies were enlightened and inspired by scientific results produced in the framework of strengthening resilience to climatic hazards:

- National government reports
- National plans for risk prevention
- National plans for the prevention of flood risks
- Communal plans of risk management
- Action plan and flood risk prevention for the cities
- Reports of design offices
- Reports of scientific expertise through specific collaborative research projects financed by national or European funds: indicators of adaptation to climate change

4.12.3 Specific limits and obstacle

In the framework of climate change, it is difficult to resolve the climatic models at the scale of the little territories of the Lesser Antilles and to produce climate knowledge by 2100. What could be the impacts of global warming on the climate hazards by 2100? How can be evaluated the rising of the sea level at the regional scale? The aggravating factors are not only due to the components of climate change. The acceleration of the urbanization is an amplifying factor that should be considering. The answers of adaptation in the case of the erosion of the beaches for example are also limited due to the smallness of the territories

4.12.4 Relevant documents

Mitigation

- National plans for risk prevention
- Regional plan for the prevention of flood risks
- The 50 geometric steps

Adaptation

- European project C3AF (Climate Change and Consequences in the F.W.I.) Website. The project is led by UA. <https://c3af.univ-montp3.fr>
- ANR project TIREX (feedback experiences on the 2017 hurricane season) on Saint-Martin (in progress)

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5 Framework additional information

5.1 Impact Chains definitions of the concepts

The scope and definitions of the concepts to be used in the context of climate change impact, vulnerability and risk assessments were done in deliverable D3.3. In this report we briefly transcribe some of most relevant inputs for the WP7 and the Framework in development:

- «**Impact Chains** as a conceptual framework allows integrating both **quantitative and qualitative** information about risks»
- «The implementation of an IC can involve a sophisticated modelling chain, or it can support quick diagnosis. ICs have the capacity to be cross-sectoral and cross-scales and allow to aggregate or **downscale risks and compare sectors.** »
- «A climate socio-economical risk is the **potential for climate - related consequences (climate impacts) for something of value** (= assets, people, ecosystem, culture, etc.). »
- « The hazard is the potential occurrence of a climate-related physical event or trends or their physical impact that may cause loss. »
- « The **exposure** is the presence of “**something of value**” in places and settings that could be adversely affected. »
- « The vulnerability is the propensity or predisposition to be adversely affected. »
- « Sensitivity may include physical attributes of a system. »
- « **Capacity** refers to the ability of societies and communities to **prepare for and respond** to current and future climate impacts. »

5.2 Energy sector complementary information

5.2.1 Previous definitions and scope from WP3

The coastal and maritime sector in SOCLIMPACT defines the scope of the energy sector with a **whole energy sector approach**, rather than just focusing on marine-related RES (Renewable Energy Sources). This is justified by the “strong relation between the energy sector and the blue economy in the islands, and the unlimited borders that blue sectors have in the context of insular economies” (D3.1 sector boundaries). In addition, “solar thermal energy (radiation exploited for solar heat)” is considered within the group of renewables as it is a widely available resource in many of the islands. “The electricity generated in pumped-storage plants is not (...)” regarded as a renewable energy source, but as a storage technology. This type of hydropower is not part of the group of resources that “replenish (or renew) themselves naturally” (D3.1 Definitions), as is the case for instance of batteries or compressed air energy storage (CAES).

A set of priority impacts were defined in D3.1 that define the focus of analysis set for marine RES generation. However, in a **whole energy sector approach** (D3.1 sector boundaries) there may be other climate impacts and risks to consider, both in the demand and supply side, however the focus on SOCLIMPACT is given by these sector boundaries. Both in adaptation and disaster risk reduction a **first approach** is proposed with a focus on the sectors' priority impacts defined in D3.1.

Finally, solutions can be explored to meet at the same time two or all three challenges of adaptation, mitigation and disaster risk reduction. For instance, as a consequence of climate change there will be shortage of drinking water in some islands which may lead to need to use technologies such as “(...) sea-water reverse osmosis desalination for covering water needs” (D3.1 Priority Impacts) which is **energy intensive**. **Increased efficiency** on all aspects of the electricity supply chain and efficiency of end used will help respond to this new energy demand. Also, taking in account the **electrification of consumption** (e.g. electric cars) and the interaction with other Blue Economy sectors “(...) the application of proper **Demand Side Management/Demand Response** will contribute to peak shaving of the island electrical demand curve, which combined with energy storage infrastructure, will allow for managing the variability and intermittence of non-dispatchable marine RES generation” (D3.1 Definitions) as well as non-marine RES. If this is achieved using smart grids, they may help to prevent failure of the energy service, speed up recovery efforts after a disaster occurrence and reduce prices for the consumer.

5.2.2 Additional climate hazards and impacts to consider

5.2.2.1 High temperature hazard on the supply side

Many “(...) conventional electric power plants area **mostly built at the shoreline** precisely to take advantage of the sea proximity as a source for refrigeration and as a sink for wastewaters” (D3.1 Definitions). Still, some power plants may rely on fresh water sources as heat sinks but “further increases in temperature and the occurrence of droughts may limit the availability of cooling water for thermal power generation in summer when the abundance of cooling water is at its lowest.” (Füssel *et al.*, 2017a). Extreme situations of **high water temperatures** (both related with the intake and discharge of water restrictions), combined with higher air temperatures can and have led to stalls or complete halts of large scale conventional power plants (Kopytko and Perkins, 2011;

McCall, Macknick and Hillman, 2016). High air temperatures also affect the efficiency and (in extreme situations) may hinder the continuity of wind and photovoltaic power, although tendencies for future change in overall production output are not fully understood. However, “regional studies on solar power generation point to very limited or neutral effects” (Füssel *et al.*, 2017a).

5.2.2.2 Heavy precipitation and flooding events

“An assessment of past trends and future projections of heavy precipitation is therefore essential for advising policy decisions on mitigation and adaptation to climate change. The risks posed by heavy precipitation hazards, such as **flooding events** (including cloud burst and flash floods) are also influenced by non-climatic factors, such as population density, floodplain development and land-use changes. Hence, estimates of future changes in such risks need to consider changes in both climatic and non-climatic factors” (Castellari *et al.*, 2017; Füssel *et al.*, 2017).

5.2.2.3 Storms, wind and sea level rise

“**Storm** location, frequency and intensity have shown considerable decadal variability across Europe (mainland) over the past century, such that no significant long-term trends are apparent.” (Füssel *et al.*, 2017a).

During **storms**, high winds and gusts (that in some cases may be around 28-32 m/s (100 km/h to 115 km/h) may **shut down wind farms** that go into their protection mode. Approaching these speeds, energy operators (utilities) may not be able to rely on this source of electricity, diverting production to other dispatchable energy sources like hydroelectricity (although run-of-the-river hydropower cannot be considered fully dispatchable during extreme weather circumstances) or fossil-fueled conventional power plants, as seen earlier (see chapter 0).

Also, breakdowns or severe weather **damages** can occur in power production or energy distribution, forcing operators to rely on backup power, usually fossil. The air and sea transport of supplies and personnel may be difficult or even impossible due to severe weather conditions. This makes it very convenient to have the necessary means *in situ*, to swiftly recover the damaged assets, in order to carry on operations. The more **isolated** islands are the **higher costs** will tend to be, regarding the availability of backup power, supplies and personnel, as they need to be ferried swiftly on demand or maintained in the island in stand-by.

Also, when **heavy seas** and **storms** are occurring, the supply of fossil fuels may be impaired or even restricted in an **isolation scenario**. This makes operators rely on fuel storage that may be placed close the sea line. Considering that “(...) a big part of the energy production, transport and distribution infrastructures are strongly linked to coastal areas” (D3.1 Definitions), this could be a **significant hazard** for islands.

5.2.2.4 Solid mass movements and the infrastructure

“Energy transport infrastructures” like electrical **energy grids** “across Europe are exposed to substantial risks from increasing frequency and magnitude of extreme events induced by climate change. Infrastructures in mountain regions will be threatened by geological instability owing to

increased precipitation.” (Füssel *et al.*, 2017a). **Soil mass movements** (landslides, mud and debris flows) and **flood risk** exist and may cause damage to energy grids and vulnerable power sources.

5.2.2.5 Wind energy resource

“The current state-of-the-art suggests no detectable change in the wind resource or other external conditions that could jeopardize the continued exploitation of wind energy in northern Europe, though further research is needed to provide greater confidence in these projections” (Pryor and Barthelmie, 2010). Furthermore, these types of projection studies use average figures for wind power over large portions of territories, but the wind impacts on land-based wind power installations may be unique to each installation.

5.2.3 Additional references

5.2.3.1 Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR)

To supplement the framework about **adaptation** and to address the creation of an integrated **disaster risk reduction (DRR)** framework, with the technical issues of the energy sector, the following work is interesting to consider:

- Estimating risk to California energy infrastructure from projected climate change (Sathaye, 2011);
- U.S. Energy Sector Vulnerabilities to Climate Change and Extreme Weather, (Zamuda *et al.*, 2013);
- The impact of climate change on the electricity market: A review (Mideksa and Kallbekken, 2010);
- Energy sector vulnerability to climate change: A review (Sugiyama, 2012);
- Sensitivity of wave energy to climate change (Gareth P. Harrison and Wallace, 2005);
- Conceptualizing energy security (Winzer, 2012);
- Critical Infrastructure Failure Interdependencies in the 2008 Chinese Winter Storms (Rong, Han and Liu, 2010).

5.2.3.2 Mitigation, 2030 climate & energy framework and the Clean Energy for Islands Initiative

The 2030 climate & energy framework aims to achieve mitigation objectives which affect the whole European space. “The framework helps drive progress towards a low-carbon economy and build an energy system that:

- ensures affordable energy for all consumers.

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- **increases the security** of the EU's energy supplies;
- reduces our dependence on energy imports;
- creates new opportunities for **growth and jobs**;
- brings **environmental and health** benefits – e.g. through reduced air pollution.”

In the islands context the European Commission has created the **Clean Energy for Islands Initiative**, recognizing that “(...) islands are particularly vulnerable to climate change, and over-dependent on fossil fuels and energy imports”. The initiative created a new “**EU Island Secretariat**” was set up to work with island communities. The Secretariat’s first task will be to gather and share best practices between EU islands and to provide technical assistance. In particular, it will:

1. promote energy **self-reliance** of islands;
2. encourage the reduction of the dependency on costly fossil fuel imports, **easing the strain**
on public budgets;
3. deliver **best available**, tailor-made solutions to boost renewable energy in the islands.

The EU will also be active at the global level in support of vulnerable island communities” (European Commission, 2018).

5.3 Maritime transports sector complementary information

5.3.1 Transport system vs transport sector

Finally, the report on “Adaptation of transport to climate change in Europe” (Georgi, 2014) makes a distinction between transport system and transport sector that may be useful to SOCLIMPACT framework both in mitigation and disaster risk reduction: “This report uses both terms. The distinction between them is not totally fixed. The **transport system** is a set of interacting components include all the transport modes, the physical elements, and the movements that contribute to the services provided by transport to the socio-economic activity (Frybourg, 1991). With **transport sector** the report instead refers to transport as a part of the economy, including its governance structure and regulating authorities.”

5.3.2 The RORO examples

For example, we can consider Roll-on/roll-off (**RORO**) terminals, designed to allow for the seamless driving of wheeled cargo, such as cars, trucks, semi-trailer trucks, trailers and railroad cars, from ships to land and vice-versa. They may be important assets in some islands as they foster a cheaper, faster and easier transfer for both goods and materials using freight, as well as passengers using all sorts of vehicles. They have several key components that are directly or indirectly vulnerable to the **sea level change**, such as the port water area (anchorage area, entrance channel,

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turning basin and harbor basin), berth and apron (provides services in support of embarking and disembarking of passengers and vehicles) and port land area (parking lot for waiting to security check, security hall, parking lot for waiting to board, auxiliary facilities and other structures) (adapted from Tang et al., 2015). It must be noted that all these components must have a wide tolerance for the height interval from each other, that allow for a wide tide height range to occur without affecting operations and at the same time endure extreme events without damage, such as storm surges.

Also, there is a water oscillation at piers requirement which is critical for stable, smooth and safe embarking and disembarking operations using RORO terminals. The water oscillation is a result of the combination of several factors, such as the resulting wave penetration regime inside the port water area which will be affected by the sea level.

5.3.3 Future trends on GMSL

“Global Mean Sea Level rise during the 21st century will very likely occur at a higher rate than during the period 1971–2010. Process-based models considered in the IPCC AR5 project a rise in sea level over the 21st century that is likely in the range of 0.26–0.54 m for a low emissions scenario (RCP2.6) and 0.45–0.81 m for a high emissions scenario (RCP8.5). However, several recent studies suggest substantially higher values. Several national assessments, expert assessments and recent model-based studies have suggested an upper bound for 21st century global mean sea level rise in the range of 1.5–2.0 m.” (Füßel *et al.*, 2017b). In (Sweet *et al.*, 2017) six scenarios were used for the increase of GMSL at the end of the century: Low (0.3 m), Intermediate-Low (0.5 m), Intermediate (1.0 m), Intermediate-High (1.5 m), High (2.0 m) and Extreme (2.5 m), having higher probabilities of exceeding GMSL (median value) the higher the RCP. It is considered that (Sweet *et al.*, 2017) may provide a useful framework for sea level rise issues in SOCLIMPACT.

It is worth mentioning that due to system **inertia**, it is expected that the GMSL will continue to rise beyond the end of the century, even for low emission pathways, but specific values have a degree of high uncertainty, as they may range from 0.39m (Low Scenario) to 9.7m (Extreme Scenario) (Sweet *et al.*, 2017). Some authors are even suggesting that “Rapid large sea level rise may begin sooner than generally assumed.” They also state that “We cannot be certain that multi-meter sea level rise will be avoided???? if we allow global warming of 2°C or beyond. However, we know the warming would continue for many centuries, if we allow it to occur (Solomon et al., 2010), a period exceeding the ice sheet response time implied by paleoclimate data. Sea level reached +6–9 m in the Eemian, a time that we have concluded was probably no more than a few tenths of a degree warmer than today (...)” (Hansen *et al.*, 2016).

5.3.4 Days below freezing, reduced ice and the Feynman Island

For the Feynman Island, **less days below freezing** will reduce problems with ice accumulation on vessels, decks, riggings and docks but increase the risk of the occurrence of dangerous ice fog that may become more frequent. Also, **reduced sea ice** will improve access to northern destinations and create longer shipping seasons near the polar region. New shipping routes, that may include other European islands that are far from this phenomenon, may arise. However, the benefits of the trade potential of Arctic transport between Europe and Asia would remain rather limited in 2050. “While this represents a small improvement for the global transport of containerized goods,

it does not justify any delay in the environmental actions necessary to protect the Arctic's fragile environment” (Füssel *et al.*, 2017b).

5.3.5 Mitigation in the maritime sector

Regarding **mitigation**, “Transport represents almost a quarter of Europe's greenhouse gas emissions and is the main cause of air pollution in cities. The transport sector has not seen the same gradual decline in emissions as other sectors: emissions only started to decrease in 2007 and still remain higher than in 1990” (European Commission, 2019d). In 2014 the navigation transport emissions share was 13% while the energy demand share was total of 11.7%. (European Commission, 2019d). Worth noting that this sector is the only transport sector that has more emission share than energy demand share, which may be considered an indicator for a lower efficiency or more carbon intensive transport sector than other transport sectors. In 2013, to help reach the 60% emissions reduction (1990 base line) in the transport sector by 2050, set by the “European Strategy for Low-Emission Mobility” (European Commission, 2016), the Commission set out a strategy towards reducing GHG emissions from the shipping industry designated “**Integrating maritime transport emissions in the EU's greenhouse gas reduction policies**” (European Commission, 2013b). “The strategy consists of 3 consecutive steps:

- Monitoring, reporting and verification of CO₂ emissions from large ships using EU ports;
- Greenhouse gas reduction targets for the maritime transport sector;
- Further measures, including market-based measures, in the medium to long term.”

“(…) the strategy includes objectives to

- reduce total annual GHG emissions from shipping by at least 50% by 2050 compared to 2008 levels;
- pursue efforts to phase them out as soon as possible in this century.

However, short-, mid- and long-term emission reduction measures, as well as research and innovation, necessary to achieve the objectives under the strategy remain to be developed and agreed” (European Commission, 2019b). It identifies relevant barriers for mitigation efforts such as “Lack of awareness about costs, benefits and return on investment regarding already available technologies seem to hinder the introduction of such technologies on a larger scale.” (European Commission, 2013b).

Additionally, “The EU has a strategic interest in ensuring the continuous performance of **short sea shipping**. As by 2050 short sea shipping has a strong role in reaching the EU transport goal of reducing 60% of greenhouse gas emission generated by transport and by 2030 the shift of 30% of road freight over 300 km to other modes” (European Commission, 2019d; D3.1 definitions and boundaries). Its main focus is to create conditions to foster this shift, which is most relevant for the main land continent but it aims to create “Motorways of the Sea” that “(…) should become part of the trans-European network (TEN-T) - just like land motorways and railways - and reduce road congestion and/or improve access to peripheral and island regions and States” (European Commission, 2019c).

5.3.6 Non-climatic factors

Considering relevant **non-climatic factors**, the marine transport sector is a complex sector with security problems and issues which are a concern of the European Commission, namely, to provide a safe environment to international trade. The EU legislation on Maritime Security is set to “The overall objective of the **EU's maritime security policy** is to protect the citizens and our economies from the consequences of unlawful intentional acts against shipping and port operations” (European Commission, 2019a). This policy is not related with climate change, but it may be necessary to address this type of issues in the SOCLIMPACT framework for adaptation.

Regarding other relevant **non-climatic factors**, the European Parliament and the Council of Ministers has established a framework, REGULATION (EU) 2017/352 - establishing a framework for the provision of **port services** and **common rules on the financial transparency** of ports (European Parliament and of the Council, 2017), for the provision of port services and common rules for the financial transparency of ports. This regulation aims to set of rules that “level the playing field in the sector”, providing a framework for operators, efficient and transparent public and private investment, definition of port services, charging of port services and infrastructure, safety and environmental requirements, mechanism to handle disputes between stakeholders and assurance of adequate work relations in ports. This European policy may also be necessary to consider in the SOCLIMPACT framework for adaptation, mitigation and disaster risk reduction.

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